

THE SPACE COURT FOUNDATION STUDENT SPACE LAW JOURNAL

**A Common Law Perspective on Space
Law Methodology** (Ben Sheridan)

**Waves of Change: The Unseen Struggle
for Radio Spectrum in Space**
(Heath Hoeffner)

**Investigating Orbital Debris Mitigation
Regime Development In the United
States** (Kaili Ayers)

Exploring Strange New Legal Worlds
(Kelsie C.M. Jackson)

**The limits of national sovereignty.
Expanding on Space Law and
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**Women in Space Law: The pending task
for more representation and visibility**
(Marieta Valdivia Lefort)

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Image: SpaceX

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ABOUT THE JOURNAL

The SCF Student Space Law Journal (SCF SSLJ) is a bi-annual, peer-reviewed publication dedicated to fostering academic excellence among students and early-career professionals in the field of space law and policy. Launched in June 2024 by the Space Court Foundation, it is the first journal exclusively for student-authored scholarship in this specialised discipline.

Aim: To offer an accessible yet exceptionally rigorous forum in which current and recent space-law students can cultivate, publish and refine scholarship of the same calibre demanded by the world's leading academic journals. By welcoming contributions from those without advanced law degrees (LLM or higher), the SCF SSLJ fills a critical gap left by traditional space-law periodicals, which seldom consider submissions from undergraduates or early-stage postgraduates, while nonetheless adhering to the highest standards of peer review and editorial excellence.

Scope: The Journal welcomes original contributions on international, regional and national dimensions of space law and policy, including but not limited to:

- Comparative analyses of national space legislation and regulatory frameworks
- Legal protection of Earth's and outer-space environments (including D&QS preservation)
- Space-traffic management (STM) and space-situational awareness (SSA)
- Satellite spectrum allocation and frequency management
- Emerging issues in space sustainability, cybersecurity and the militarisation of space
- Regulatory and ethical considerations for AI and automated decision-making in space activities
- Policy developments relating to commercial, environmental and public-interest uses of outer space

All submissions undergo double-blind peer review in accordance with the most exacting professional standards. Moreover, as part of our internship programme, SCF interns may submit abstracts and, if accepted, are paired with a dedicated mentor who guides them through the drafting and structuring of a professional manuscript, while ensuring they retain full academic ownership of their ideas and prose.

Further information about the SCF SSLJ can be found on our website.

SPACE COURT LAW LIBRARY MASTHEAD

Work on the Space Court Law Library brings together scholars and students from around the world to collaborate on a range of research projects. Together, these projects will form a comprehensive and accessible online space law reference library. It will ultimately be home to the most complete repository of primary source legal documents related to national and international space law, both private and public.

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NOTE FROM THE EDITOR-IN-CHIEF OF THE SPACE COURT LAW LIBRARY

As Editor-in-Chief, it is my great privilege to welcome readers to this inaugural issue of the SCF Student Journal. This publication marks an exciting milestone for the Space Court Foundation, representing the first in an enduring series dedicated to providing students and young professionals a platform to publish their insights on space law and policy. At SCF, we promote space law education and the rule of law. To meet these aspirations, we strongly believe in empowering the next generation by amplifying their voices and fostering their involvement in critical space-related discussions through scholarship.

Launching a new journal is no small feat, and the success of this first volume is a testament to the dedication, collaboration, and intellectual rigor of our contributors and editorial team. I would like to extend my heartfelt gratitude to every student and young professional who contributed their work, ideas, and enthusiasm. Your commitment has set a high standard for future editions and enriched our community immensely.

Special acknowledgement must go to Yana Yakushina and Jonathan Kaley-Isley, whose tireless efforts in editing, managing submissions, and guiding authors through the publication process were instrumental in bringing this journal to fruition. Their meticulous attention to detail, unwavering support, and leadership have made this endeavor not only possible but exemplary.

As we celebrate this inaugural issue, we look forward to the ongoing contributions of our vibrant SCF community. Together, we are building more than just a journal; we are nurturing a space for emerging scholars and professionals to shape the future of space law and policy. Thank you all for your dedication and enthusiasm, I eagerly anticipate seeing how this publication grows and evolves in the coming years.

— Christopher HEARSEY
Editor-in-Chief, SCF Space Court Law Library
June 2025

FOREWORD

It is with great pride that we present this issue of the Space Court Foundation Student Space Law Journal (SCF SSLJ). In an era of unprecedented growth in space activities, driven by both state and private actors, the need for fresh perspectives and innovative legal analysis has never been greater. Yet, until now, there has been no open, dedicated space law journal for students and young professionals to enter the scholarly conversation at the highest level.

The Space Court Foundation established this Journal to empower a new generation of space-law thinkers. We believe that by lowering traditional barriers to publication and providing structured editorial mentorship, we can cultivate talent, stimulate debate, and advance the rule of space law. The contributions in this issue, ranging from comparative examinations of national regulatory frameworks to visionary essays on sustainability, dark-sky preservation, and the governance of autonomous space systems, reflect the breadth and depth of contemporary space law scholarship.

We are grateful to our authors, reviewers, and editorial team for their dedication to upholding the exacting standards of academic integrity and clarity that underpin the SCF SSLJ. As you explore these pages, we hope you share our conviction that today's students will become tomorrow's leaders in crafting the legal frameworks that govern humanity's final frontier.

— Editors, SCF Student Space Law Journal
June 2025

INTRODUCING THE NEW SCF INITIATIVE “WOMEN IN SPACE LAW”

WOMEN IN SPACE LAW: THE PENDING TASK FOR MORE REPRESENTATION AND VISIBILITY

Marieta Valdivia Lefort

Latin America Legal Research Officer, SCF

The global scenario for the space sector has significantly changed in the last decade. The sector has witnessed a dramatic increase in its growth and development, including an increase in countries' investment in space exploration and more commercial rocket launches, which has also contributed to the overcrowding of the space environment. All together, this general

growth has raised concerns linked to the sustainable use of space and the need for governance and regulation as the industry evolves, increasing the interest in the field of space law and the number of students and professionals involved in the field. Indeed, more people are interested and involved in space law today, however, the representation and visibility of women in this field are still pending tasks.

In the space sector in general, despite the progressive increase in the popularity of initiatives related to inclusivity and equity, there is ample evidence of the lack of representation of women, as highlighted by the United Nations Office for Outer Space Affairs (UNOOSA) Space4Women programme, whose aim is encouraging women and girls to pursue Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics (STEM) education and raising awareness about career opportunities and the importance of gender equality and empowerment in the space sector. Indeed, women have remained historically underrepresented in the space sector and prominent roles; in the last three decades, women have represented 20-22% of the total space industry workforce. Despite this, some actions, such as the appointment of UNOOSA's current Director, Aarti Holla-Maini (2023 – incumbent) and previously Simonetta Di Pippo's appointment for the same role (2014-2022), have challenged this tendency, representing a step forward in women's representation and visibility in the space sector and on high positions.

Nevertheless, some areas linked to the space sector are somehow excluded from the discussion when it comes to the representation and visibility of women, specifically the ones linked to the humanities and the social sciences. One example of this is space law, which is similarly to STEM, a highly male-dominated field. Indeed, the represen-

ation of women in space law is a topic that started to receive certain attention recently, raising questions about the need to increase the number of women in the field, but also the visibility of those who are already involved in it. Furthermore, there is also a need for advancing research regarding the barriers to increasing representation and equality in this field, at both the educational/formation level and the work/practice one. It is likely that many of the barriers somehow mirror the classic obstacles identified in the literature on STEM-related fields, including stereotypes in the workplace and gender-based discriminatory comments.

Nevertheless, and despite the potential similarity with what women in STEM experience, exploring these barriers for space law in particular and as a separate realm is a mandatory task that deserves attention. Furthermore, since the space industry requires lawyers across many different practice areas, the question of representation and visibility should not be simplified to the general field of space law.

While defence has been the traditional focus for space law, the current scenario of the space sector demands a much broader range of commercial legal support, and therefore, the question of women representation and visibility should reflect the situation in each of these areas, including technology, telecommunications, insurance, property, among others. Some of these areas, such as telecommunications, tend to be strongly male-dominated, and therefore, the question of representation and visibility of women becomes even more relevant.

“WHEN 50% OF THE WORLD’S POPULATION ARE WOMEN, GENDER EQUALITY IS NOT ONLY THE RIGHT THING TO DO, BUT IT IS ALSO THE SMART THING TO DO.” DIRECTOR OF UNOOSA ARTI HOLLA-MAINI

The above is precisely why this initiative was created: to highlight the names of women working in space law to foster recognition and future participation of young female professionals. To do this, we will narrate the trajectories of women who are or were actively involved in the field, emphasising their processes to overcome obstacles, why they decided to continue in the field, and suggestions for future female colleagues. Indeed, at Space Court Foundation (SCF) we are committed to contributing to reducing this gap, and these columns are part of a broader ‘Women in Space Law’ project organised by the SCF, which also features a podcast to discuss women’s experiences in the field and strategies to overcome challenges, so stay tuned!.

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A Common Law Perspective on Space Law Methodology

Ben Sheridan¹

ABSTRACT

Common law is more than just the legal system that pervades much of the English-speaking world. It is a unique method of forming and applying law. Increasingly, the development of space law is shifting towards a civil law approach. Such a tendency has the dangerous potential to stifle the development of high-quality space law. This paper presents a common law perspective on the development of space law. In the first part, it demonstrates the civil law orthodoxy that exists in space law. In the second part, it sets out the distinctive structural features of the common law and demonstrates how they may be of use to space lawyers. Specifically, a common law approach can improve the fairness of decision-making, improve the law-making process, and enable more countries to contribute to space law. In the third part, it examines potential drawbacks of a common law approach and addresses those concerns.

KEYWORDS: common law, space law, civil law, decision-making

1. INTRODUCTION

Common law is the main legal system throughout much of the English-speaking world. Originally the legal system of England and Wales, it spread across the globe due through the influence of the British Empire.² It includes such countries as Australia, India, Malta, the United States (except state law in Louisiana and Puerto Rico), and Zimbabwe, to name just a few.³ Common law jurisdictions are identifiable by their distinctive characteristics. Foremost among these are: judge-made law, precedent, flexibility, case-based law-making, and published law-reports.⁴ By contrast, civil law, the other main type of legal system in the world, owes its roots to Roman law, specifically Emperor Justinian's *Corpus Juris Civilis*.⁵ In the 19th century, a number of national civil codes were promulgated, notably France's Napoleonic *Code Civil* in 1804 and Germany's *Bürgerliches Gesetzbuch* ('BGB') in 1900. The drafters of civil codes aimed to create comprehensive documents to clearly set out the law. Unlike common law, civil law systems place less

¹ Space Court Foundation Intern, ben.sheridan@spacecourtfoundation.org

² Joseph Dainow, 'The civil law and the common law: some points of comparison' (1967) 15 American Journal of Comparative Law 3, at 424.

³ Sandra F. Joireman, 'Colonization and the Rule of Law: Comparing the effectiveness of common law and civil law countries' (2004) Political Science Faculty Publications, at 38.

⁴ Dainow (n 2), at 424.

⁵ *Ibid.* at 421.

importance on the doctrine of precedent and give their judges little power to change the law.⁶ Although being part of the same type of jurisdiction, civil law countries can have significant differences in their laws. By contrast, common law countries share much substantive law, and judgments in one common law country often examine the law in other common law jurisdictions. A persuasive judgment from one common law country even has a weak power of precedent in other common law countries.

Increasingly, both at the national level and international level, space law is adopting a civil law approach. This paper will identify flaws with this. Second, a number of structural advantages of common law will be examined and their potential utility in space law will be demonstrated. Notably, in terms of improving the quality of decision-making, elevating the quality of debate, and enabling more countries to contribute to space law. Finally, concerns regarding the adoption of this common law approach will be acknowledged and assuaged.

2. CIVIL LAW ORTHODOXY IN SPACE LAW

2.1 Domestic law

Across the world, academics and practitioners call for increased space law regulation.⁷ Through lobbying and advocacy, they seek to take advantage of the time and breathing space that humanity has now to develop laws to ensure that space is used in a manner that benefits humanity before industry lobbyists and vested interests distort the law-making process. Such an argument is attractive but marks an evolution in the development of space law. Domestic legislation used to have to catch up with technological agreements and international agreements. A good example of this is the passage in the UK of the Outer Space Act (OSA) in 1986 – 19 years after the Outer Space Treaty (the obligations from which the OSA sought to bring into domestic law). Recently, however, countries have passed laws regulating activities that have not yet occurred nor are likely to happen in the immediate future. For example, Luxembourg⁸ and the US⁹ have both legislated to create legal frameworks that regulate mining resources in space. The crucial point that these developments illustrate is that domestic space law is very unusual in that it is, in places, further ahead than the technology which might support the activities that it seeks to regulate.

2.2 International law

Harmonisation between countries' space law is increasingly breaking down. For example, the 2020 Artemis Accords have few signatories outside of Western countries.¹⁰ The long-term impact of such a break-down in consensus could well be a fracturing of goodwill and cooperation. This would be very problematic given that international agreements have recognised the importance of cooperation in space. For example, Article I OST requires states to “encourage international co-operation” with regard to scientific investigation.¹¹ Picker argues that what often sets a civil law approach apart from international law is that civil law typically develops by theory whereas international law develops by compromises between nations forced by

⁶ Francis Deak, ‘Place of the case in the common and the civil law’ (1933-1934) 8 *Tulane Law Review* 3, at 344.

⁷ See David A. Epstein, ‘Protecting the Cosmos: The Need to Define Celestial Bodies in the Outer Space Treaty’ (2023) 47 *Journal of Space Law* 2; Adriana ‘Ana’ Santana, ‘Options for a Liability Framework for Commercial Low-Earth Orbit Destinations’ (2024) 49 *Air and Space Law* (4/5).

⁸ Law of July 20, 2017 on the exploration and use of space resources. https://space-agency.public.lu/en/agency/legal-framework/law_space_resources_english_translation.html

⁹ US Commercial Space Launch Competitiveness Act of 2015, s.402. <https://www.congress.gov/bill/114th-congress/house-bill/2262>

¹⁰ Artemis Accords. <https://www.nasa.gov/artemis-accords/>

¹¹ *Treaty on Principles Governing the Activities of States in the Exploration and Use of Outer Space, including the Moon and Other Celestial Bodies*. United Nations Office for Outer Space Affairs. (n.d.), Article I. <https://www.unoosa.org/oosa/en/ourwork/spacelaw/treaties/introouterspacetreaty.html>

necessity.¹² Increasingly, however, space law is being developed by theory not necessity. The International Law Association (ILA) in its draft convention on dispute resolution mechanisms for space law has proposed that the International Court of Justice (ICJ) have jurisdiction over disputes between countries in space.¹³ Notably, there is no concept of *stare decisis* in the ICJ; indeed, its constitutive treaty explicitly precludes its decisions from having precedential value.¹⁴

3. LESSONS FROM COMMON LAW

3.1 *Quality of decision making*

Common law is created by judges' responses to specific facts in cases.¹⁵ This confronts judges with the immediate consequences of their decisions. For example, a legislator passing legislation on contract law will likely not have the same emotional response as, for example, Lord Reid in *Beswick v Beswick*,¹⁶ who, confronted with the reality of a "grossly unjust"¹⁷ quantum of damages, adopted a more flexible remedy to avoid injustice. The humanity of judges, therefore, is an important safety net. It ensures that the focus of the judgment is on the parties in the case. This becomes even more relevant for space law. The legislator passing the housing bill can hear testimonials from tenants, summon experts who have empirically analysed the impact of policies, and have a degree of first-hand experience. Much of this is absent from space activities. Therefore, none of the present safeguards that legislators can use to bring stakeholders into the law-making process can be applied in the space law context. In the absence of such safeguards, it is essential that the courts act as a safety net that protects against the limitations of bureaucracy.

Flexibility is also a key feature of common law. Indeed, Carbello has suggested that this flexibility in the context of a fast-moving legal environment is one of the reasons why Dubai chose to adopt common law in 2006.¹⁸ Flexibility will likely prove highly important for space law. It is impossible for Earth-bound lawyers to anticipate every eventuality that will arise in space. There will inevitably be gaps and inconsistencies. Therefore, the quality of decision making will be markedly better if judges are able to respond to practical situations. Consider, for example, *force majeure*. The English case of *Matsoukis v Priestman & Co* held that while industrial action can count as *force majeure*, bad weather cannot.¹⁹ Legislators are not currently in a position now to make evidence-backed determinations of the existence and scope of hazards in space. This can only be informed by the facts of specific cases. Judges should not be hamstrung by rigid constraints of national codes that purport to provide a comprehensive set of rules.

3.2 *Elevating the quality of debate*

Structures within common law promote a healthy dialogue between judges, legislatures, and academics. A key reason for this is that laws can be tested out and the fairness of judgments carefully analysed. This was well illustrated in the saga of UK tort litigation concerning asbestos-related injury. In order to preserve

¹² Colin B. Picker, 'International Law's Mixed Heritage: A Common/Civil Law Jurisdiction' (2008) 41 *Vanderbilt Journal of Transnational Law* 4, at 1101.

¹³ Space Law Committee of the International Law Association, 'Draft Convention on the Settlement of Space Law Disputes adopted by the Space Law Committee of the International Law Association' (1998) *International Outer Space Law*, Volume 7, Part 3, at 734.

¹⁴ *Statute of the International Court of Justice*, Article 59.

¹⁵ Deak (n 6).

¹⁶ [1967] 2 All ER 1197.

¹⁷ *Ibid.* at 1202.

¹⁸ Alejandro Carballo, 'The Law of the Dubai International Financial Centre: Common Law Oasis or Mirage Within the UAE?' (2007) 21 *Arab Law Quarterly* 1, at 99.

¹⁹ [1915] 1 K.B. 681.

consistency in the (non-statutory) law of causation, the House of Lords in *Barker v Corus*²⁰ handed down a decision that significantly restricted the ability of victims of asbestos exposure to recover damages. The UK Parliament responded rapidly to public pressure to create an exception to the normal rules of causation for asbestos.²¹ This achieved a well-balanced outcome that preserved clear rules of causation whilst ensuring that asbestos victims were able to recover damages for negligence. Such a solution would not have been foreseeable in advance of the litigation. It is only by stress-testing rules and developing doctrines accordingly that the law can properly respond to the needs of litigating parties.

The best way to test whether a law will function well or not is to test if it survives contact with reality. The folly of formulating law without consideration for practical concerns was highlighted by the German legal theorist Rudolph von Jhering. He posited the existence of the ‘Begriffshimmel’ – a heaven of juristic concepts far removed from the real world.²² The thought experiment set out the idea that effective laws cannot be formulated in the abstract. Common law jurisdictions all demonstrate a strong commitment to law reporting. By contrast, civil law jurisdictions often do not have official law reporting.²³ These are practices which would, if applied to the space law context, contribute to an ongoing process of refinement.

3.3 Inclusive Space Law

It is vital that the development of space law should be able to take into account views from all across the world. It is here that one of the biggest concerns with the civil law method of space law making emerges. If the world develops a space law regime formulated by major players such as the US, China, the EU, and the UK, then there is a real risk that the opinions of swathes of humankind will be ignored. Henrich has argued that there are many moral judgments upon which people in Western countries reach different conclusions to the rest of the world. He notes, for example, the importance of *mens rea* in determining blameworthiness.²⁴ Specifically, he states that individuals in Western countries tend to describe someone as less blameworthy if they lacked intent.²⁵ This is just a small demonstration of a wider problem; imposing substantial law of a certain character is an insult to countries who wield less diplomatic clout. In common law, attitudes from numerous countries are pooled and considered. There are countless English private law cases where the law from countries including Canada, Australia, and the US, is examined, analysed, and applied or not according to consideration of all the necessary factors. For example, the UK Supreme Court in *Patel v Mirza*²⁶ discussed at length the judgment of the Supreme Court of Canada (SCR) in *Hall v Hebert*,²⁷ referring to the explanation that McLachlin J gave for the rationale behind the illegality defence.²⁸ This demonstrates that common law enables judges to draw on an international wealth of thinking. For example, in *Barlow v Clowes*,²⁹ an English trusts case, there was substantial discussion as to whether the “North American” method of recovering assets in bankruptcy should be used. The Court of Appeal decided not to adopt the North American approach – concluding that the complications involved in implementing that approach were too great.³⁰

²⁰ [2006] UKHL 20.

²¹ Compensation Act 2006, s.3. <https://www.legislation.gov.uk/ukpga/2006/29/contents>

²² Rudolf von Jhering, ‘Im juristischen Begriffshimmel’, ‘Von Jhering, Scherz Und Ernst In Der Jurisprudenz’ (11th ed. 1912), 245.

²³ Deak (n 6), at 341.

²⁴ Joseph P. Henrich, *The weirdest people in the world: How the west became psychologically peculiar and particularly prosperous* (Penguin Books 2021).

²⁵ *Ibid.*

²⁶ [2016] UKSC 42.

²⁷ [1993] 2 SCR 159.

²⁸ (n 20), [59]

²⁹ [1992] 4 All ER 22.

³⁰ *Ibid.* at 43.

This style of judgment greatly enhances the quality of debate. It ensures that domestic laws are properly considered and compared to alternatives. It also gives courts a much larger pool of expertise and knowledge to draw upon in formulating the law. By contrast, a civil law approach risks creating lawyers who are experts in their narrow jurisdictions but cannot think beyond. An approach that takes into account non-major countries is particularly important given the need to avoid perpetuating colonial attitudes – or even creating new ones. Van Eijk and Aganaba argue that in decolonising international law, it is not enough to simply include countries such as those in Africa in discussions about space law.³¹ They must have power to actually influence law-making. For example, perhaps there should be a single international court that should have jurisdiction over disputes between countries in space. It should draw upon legal expertise from across the world by being staffed by a diverse judiciary.

4. ADDRESSING CONCERNS

4.1 Uncertainty

The main argument against such a common law approach is purported uncertainty. The argument runs as follows: 1) legal certainty is a prerequisite for private entities being willing to engage in the space activities, 2) a civil law approach is better at achieving legal certainty, therefore, 3) a common law approach will stifle space innovation. This argument is important. Hart, for example, argues that the most important purpose that law serves is “providing guides to human conduct”.³² Applying this argument to space law rests on the premise that certainty is best achieved by setting out clear rules from the outset. This argument can be countered by noting that legal certainty has more to do with the substance of the law, not the structure. To take an example from the law of contract, many commercial entities value English law for the legal certainty it delivers. In particular, the lack of a general requirement of good faith. The fact that England is a common law jurisdiction and France is a civil law jurisdiction is not the reason why England has no requirement of good faith,³³ yet France has one.³⁴ Indeed, the fact that common law fosters dialogue between Parliament, courts, academics, and judges may be one of the reasons why England has retained this aspect of its contract law which is seen by some as a crucial aspect of the popularity of the UK as a place to do business. By giving judges law-making powers, they may feel a greater sense of responsibility. For example, in *Re Spectrum Plus Ltd*,³⁵ the House of Lords acknowledged that “[t]he commercial life of [the United Kingdom] depends upon the reliability of the security arrangements that are entered into between debtors and their creditors”.³⁶ Judges therefore feel a great weight of responsibility to minimise secondary consequences of their judgments.

Even if it is conceded that the structure of law has some role to play in affecting legal certainty, it does not necessarily follow that the structure of common law is ill-suited at achieving legal certainty. Courts are frequently confronted with novel situations where the law may be incomplete. Yet they resolve cases by using well-established legal principles.³⁷ Perhaps legislators could begin by setting out general principles and then develop more substantive law as specific issues arise. For example, the principle of *nemo dat quod*

³¹ Cristian van Eijk and Timiebi Aganaba, ‘Inspired by Africa: A New Approach to Global Space Governance’ (2021) 9 *New Space* 1, at 1-4.

³² HLA Hart, Joseph Raz and Penelope A. Bulloch, *The Concept of Law* (3rd edn, OUP 2012), at 249.

³³ See, e.g., *Walford v Miles*, [1992] 2 AC 128.

³⁴ *Code Civil*, Article 1104.

³⁵ [2005] 2 AC 680.

³⁶ *Ibid.* at 706.

³⁷ Ronald Dworkin, *Law’s Empire* (1st ed, Hart 1998), at 19.

non habet could provide an important basis for judges to formulate more substantive space property law upon.

4.2 *The inadequacy of customary international law*

The most striking aspect of the development of space law in response to events – not abstract theory – is the rapid formation of the rule of customary international law of freedom of movement into outer space. For example, Judge Lachs in the *North Sea Continental Shelf Case*³⁸ noted the rule was established “within a remarkably short period of time”. General practice and *opinio juris* were rapidly established after “the launching States sought no permission, nor did the other States protest.” Judge Lachs uses this as an example to demonstrate the fact that law must respond to “the great acceleration of social and economic change, combined with that of science and technology”.³⁹ Is custom adequate for progressive development or is it necessary for there to be an international space court with universal and supreme jurisdiction that can develop rules according to *stare decisis*? Arguably, in its current form, rules on the development of customary international law are inadequate to meet the demands of space law. In particular, this is because of the contradiction inherent in the *opinio juris* requirement; custom can only arise after states have acted in a certain way “based on their being conscious of having a duty to” act or abstain.⁴⁰ Perhaps such a formulation was a pragmatic way to identify custom when international law was ill-defined and protean. But in the 21st century, such an approach is woefully ill-suited to reflecting the dominant role that positive law plays compared to natural law. A good illustration of this can be seen by analysing the treatment of the ILC Draft Articles on the Immunity of State officials from foreign criminal jurisdiction. In particular, Article 7 was criticised for not being *lex lata*.⁴¹ The ILC is in an impossible position; it is very difficult to progressively develop the law through custom when international law rules are so well documented that the *opinio juris* fiction is nigh-on impossible to achieve in practice. Another problem with customary international law is the exemption that exists for persistent objectors.⁴² It would be unfeasible for only some states to be bound by international norms in space. A court of compulsory, supreme jurisdiction would resolve this problem; disunity will breed distrust and make international law-making impossible.

5. CONCLUSION

The purpose of this paper has not been to argue the superiority of common law over civil law. Rather, it has sought to challenge what appear to be orthodox positions that have taken hold in space jurisprudence. The key point has been to argue that the current focus of academics and legislators should be to ask less ‘what should the law be?’ and more ‘how should legal systems be structured to respond to the ongoing legal issues that will arise in relation to space law?’. By analysing common law methodology, it has been argued that valuable lessons can be learned that might elevate the quality of debate and improve law-making.

³⁸ *North Sea Continental Shelf (Federal Republic of Germany/Netherlands)*, [1969] ICJ 1.

³⁹ *Ibid.* at 230.

⁴⁰ *Lotus case, (France v. Turkey) (1927) P.C.I.J., Ser. A, No. 10*, [76] (Majority opinion).

⁴¹ Rosanne van Alebeek, ‘The “International Crime” Exception in the ILC Draft Articles on the Immunity of State Officials from Foreign Criminal Jurisdiction: Two Steps Back?’ (2018) *AJIL Unbound*, at 27.

⁴² See, e.g., *Colombia v Peru, ‘Asylum Case’*, [1950] ICJ 6 278.

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Waves of Change: The Unseen Struggle for Radio Spectrum in Space

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ABSTRACT

The rapid expansion of space activities necessitates effective radio frequency spectrum management and allocation, which are crucial for the sustainability and safety of space operations. As space becomes increasingly congested with satellites and other technologies, the potential for signal interference and conflicts over spectrum rights grows significantly. This paper examines the pivotal role of radio frequency spectrum management in space law, emphasizing its underrepresentation in current policy discussions.

Radio frequency spectrum is a finite and essential resource for all space-based operations, including communication, navigation, and Earth observation. The increasing number of small satellites and mega-constellations poses significant challenges to spectrum allocation and management, leading to heightened risks of signal interference and operational conflicts. Current regulatory frameworks, while foundational, struggle to keep pace with rapid technological advancements and the proliferation of space activities.

Despite its critical importance, radio frequency spectrum management often takes a back seat in policy discussions, overshadowed by more visible aspects of space exploration and commercialization. This underrepresentation can lead to inadequate regulatory responses and increased potential for disputes. Effective spectrum management requires a coordinated approach involving international bodies, national governments, and private entities to ensure fair and sustainable use of this vital resource.

In the context of space law, proactive and forward-thinking strategies are essential to address the complexities of spectrum allocation. Emphasizing the need for enhanced collaboration and robust policy frameworks can help mitigate risks and promote sustainable growth in space activities. By prioritizing radio frequency spectrum management, the space law community can better navigate the challenges of an increasingly crowded and competitive space environment.

KEYWORDS: radio-frequency spectrum management, spectrum allocation, space law, signal interference, mega-constellations

1. OVERVIEW OF RADIO FREQUENCY SPECTRUM MANAGEMENT

1.1 Definition and Importance of Spectrum Management

Spectrum management refers to the process of regulating the use of radio frequencies to promote efficient utilization and avoid interference among different users. It involves the allocation, assignment, and monitoring of radio frequencies across various services, such as broadcasting, telecommunications,

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satellite, communications, and more. The important spectrum management lies, and its ability to ensure that the finite resource of the radio frequency spectrum is used effectively to support a wide range of applications critical to moderate society, including emergency, emergency services, defense, aviation, and space exploration.²

Effective spectrum management is crucial for maintaining the functionality and reliability of communication systems. Without it, there would be an increased risk of interference between different radio frequency users, leading to disruptions and services that could have significant societal, economic, and security implications. Increasing demand for wireless communication services, driven by the proliferation of mobile devices, satellite systems, and emerging technology, such as 5G underscore the importance of sound spectrum management practices.³

1.2 Current Usage, Trends, and Challenges

The usage of the radio frequency spectrum has evolved significantly over the past few decades, reflecting advancement of technology, and changing societal needs. Some key turns and the exponential growth in the number of wireless devices, including smartphones, tablets, and other connected technologies, have significantly increased demand for radio frequency spectrum. This rising demand places considerable pressure on regulators to allocate spectrum efficiently and equitably. Because spectrum is a finite resource, overcrowding can result in signal interference, reduced quality of service, and data transmission delays.⁴ These issues affect not only consumers but also critical operations such as aviation, emergency response, and satellite communications that require reliable and interference-free access to spectrum. The challenge lies in balancing the needs of commercial, public, and scientific users while developing innovative strategies to manage spectrum congestion and maintain its long-term sustainability

The growing number of satellites, particularly in Low Earth Orbit (LEO), has significantly increased demand for radio frequency spectrum within the space sector. As more satellite systems are deployed, particularly by commercial operators launching large constellations, the risk of interference and signal congestion also rises. This trend has made effective spectrum sharing and coordination increasingly difficult, as numerous stakeholders now compete for access to the same finite spectrum resources. Ensuring reliable, interference-free transmissions while preserving equitable access has become a pressing concern for regulators and international organizations working to manage frequency bands.⁵

As spectrum management is not just a national issue, it requires international coordination to ensure that cross-border interference is minimized. That is particularly important for services like satellite communications and aviation, where signals cross national boundaries. In satellite communications, for example, signals transmitted from satellites orbiting above multiple countries can interfere with each other if not properly coordinated. Similarly, aviation systems rely on signals for communication and navigation as aircraft travel across various international airspaces. Such interdependence necessitates global cooperation to ensure uninterrupted services and prevent interference between nations. International bodies, such as the International Telecommunication Union (ITU), play a critical role in facilitating cooperation and establishing global standards for spectrum management by coordinating the allocation of frequency bands across countries to prevent interference. The ITU provides a platform for member states to negotiate and agree on global spectrum policies, ensuring that each country adheres to a harmonized set of rules that

² Walker, J. (2023, September 27). *Spectrum overview*. NASA. <https://www.nasa.gov/directorates/somd/space-communications-navigation-program/spectrum-overview/>

³ Krishan, N. (2023, September 6). *NTIA looks to modernize federal spectrum systems as demand for 5G, space commerce skyrockets*. FedScoop. <https://fedscoop.com/ntia-looks-to-modernize-federal-spectrum-systems-as-demand-for-5g-space-commerce-skyrockets/>

⁴ *Ibid.*

⁵ Whipple, T. (2024, September 18). *SpaceX: FCC should revise spectrum sharing between satellite types*. Broadband Breakfast. <https://broadbandbreakfast.com/spacex-fcc-should-revise-spectrum-sharing-between-satellite-types/>

promotes efficient spectrum use. It also conducts regular reviews and updates to spectrum regulations in response to new technologies and evolving needs, helping to manage the growing demand for spectrum in sectors like satellite communications and aviation. By offering guidelines and resolving conflicts between nations, the ITU ensures that global communication networks, including those that rely on satellite signals or air traffic control systems, can operate seamlessly across borders.⁶

With the increasing activity in the radio spectrum, there is a growing need to protect “quiet skies” - areas free from artificial radio noise. This is essential for scientific research, particularly in radio astronomy, where even minimal interference can disrupt observations because cosmic signals are extremely weak and easily drowned out by human-made transmissions. Balancing the protection of these quiet zones with the demand for more spectrum is a significant challenge for regulators.⁷

In summary, the management of radio frequency spectrum is a complex and dynamic field that requires ongoing attention to evolving technologies and usage patterns. As society becomes more reliant on wireless communications, the challenges associated with spectrum management will only become more pronounced, necessitating innovative approaches and robust regulatory frameworks.

2. LEGAL AND REGULATORY FRAMEWORKS FOR SPECTRUM MANAGEMENT IN SPACE

2.1 International Regulations and Oversight

In space law, the regulation of radio frequency spectrum is governed primarily by international treaties and agreements under the auspices of the ITU, a specialized agency of the United Nations. The ITU’s Radio Regulations govern the global allocation of frequency bands, ensuring that radio services in space can operate without harmful interference.⁸

The Radio Regulations are legally binding for ITU member states, and they allocate specific frequency bands to various satellite services, including communications, Earth observation, and navigation. The ITU coordinates these frequencies to prevent overlap and interference, ensuring efficient use of the finite spectrum resource in an increasingly congested space environment.⁹

The *Outer Space Treaty* (OST) of 1967, while not directly regulating radio frequencies, underpins the broader framework of international cooperation and peaceful use of outer space, which includes frequency management.¹⁰ States must avoid harmful interference with the space activities of other nations, a principle supported by the ITU’s coordination efforts. While the ITU allocates frequencies and establishes international guidelines, it is up to individual countries to implement these standards through their domestic regulatory frameworks. This interaction ensures national systems align with international obligations, promoting consistency and reducing conflict

⁶ ITU-R: Managing the radio-frequency spectrum for the world. ITU. (n.d.). <https://www.itu.int/en/mediacentre/backgrounders/Pages/itu-r-managing-the-radio-frequency-spectrum-for-the-world.aspx>

⁷ *IAU WG6 Session: Executive Working Group on Dark & Quiet Sky Protection*. IAU CPS. (2024, August 14). <https://cps.iau.org/meetings/iauga24cps/iauga24wg6/>

⁸ *Ibid.* at 5.

⁹ *Idid.*

¹⁰ *Treaty on Principles Governing the Activities of States in the Exploration and Use of Outer Space, including the Moon and Other Celestial Bodies*. United Nations Office for Outer Space Affairs. (n.d.). <https://www.unoosa.org/oosa/en/ourwork/spacelaw/treaties/introouterspacetreaty.html>

2.2 National and Regional Spectrum Policies

On a national level, countries implement spectrum allocation and licensing through their domestic regulatory agencies. For example, in the United States, the Federal Communications Commission (FCC) and the National Telecommunications and Information Administration (NTIA) oversee spectrum management for commercial¹¹ and governmental uses¹², respectively. These agencies ensure that satellite operators comply with both ITU regulations and national requirements by reviewing license applications, coordinating spectrum assignments with international bodies, monitoring signal use to prevent interference, and enforcing compliance through regulatory actions and penalties.

Regional bodies like the European Conference of Postal and Telecommunications Administrations (CEPT) play a role in harmonizing spectrum management policies among European states, ensuring that satellites can operate across borders without encountering regulatory inconsistencies.

2.3 Challenges in International and Domestic Coordination

The current legal frameworks, while comprehensive, face challenges in keeping pace with rapid technological advancements. The rise of small satellites, mega-constellations, and commercial space ventures complicates frequency coordination because these systems dramatically increase the number of users operating simultaneously in overlapping frequency bands. This not only heightens the risk of harmful interference but also places significant strain on existing coordination mechanisms, which were not designed to handle the sheer volume and complexity of modern satellite constellations. As a result, disputes over orbital slots and spectrum allocation are growing as the space domain becomes increasingly competitive and congested.

In particular, mega-constellations such as SpaceX's Starlink and Amazon's Project Kuiper, are placing unprecedented demands on available spectrum, because they involve thousands of satellites transmitting large volumes of data simultaneously, often using the same or adjacent frequency bands. This intensive use increases the risk of signal interference and limits the availability of spectrum for other operators. As a result, concerns are growing over potential monopolization and overcrowding of frequency bands.¹³ The international community is grappling with how to ensure equitable access to spectrum for emerging space nations and private companies.

2.4 Emerging Legal Issues: Quiet and Dark Skies

A growing concern in space law is the protection of quiet and dark skies from the interference caused by radio emissions and artificial light from satellites.¹⁴ These concerns intersect with spectrum management as radio interference can disrupt not only satellite operations but also scientific observations and ground-based radio astronomy. In radio astronomy, even the faintest radio signals can be critical for observing distant cosmic phenomena, such as stars, galaxies, and interstellar particles. Artificial radio emissions from satellites can drown out these signals, making it difficult for astronomers to gather accurate data. Additionally, ground-based radio observatories rely on minimal electromagnetic interference to maintain

¹¹ *About the FCC.* Federal Communications Commission. (n.d.). <https://www.fcc.gov/about/overview#:~:text=The%20FCC's%20Mission,of%20Columbia%20and%20U.S.%20territories>

¹² *About NTIA.* National Telecommunications and Information Administration. (n.d.). <https://www.ntia.gov/page/about-ntia#:~:text=NTIA's%20programs%20and%20policymaking%20focus,continued%20innovation%20and%20economic%20growth>

¹³ Zisk R. (2024, March 28). *Starlink's FCC request for more spectrum denied.* Payload. [https://payloadspace.com/starlink-argues-over-spectrum-in-iran/#:~:text=Starlink's%20bid%20for%20more%20spectrum,Globalstar%20\(%24GSAT\)%20and%20Dish](https://payloadspace.com/starlink-argues-over-spectrum-in-iran/#:~:text=Starlink's%20bid%20for%20more%20spectrum,Globalstar%20(%24GSAT)%20and%20Dish)

¹⁴ *Id.* at 6.

the integrity of their observations, and the increasing number of satellites in orbit raises the risk of signal overlap, further hindering their research. The ITU and national regulators must navigate how to balance commercial needs with the protection of scientific and environmental interests, ensuring that the drive for technological development does not come at the expense of fundamental research in space science.

As space activities continue to expand, legal frameworks will need to evolve to manage these new challenges, ensuring that spectrum use remains fair, efficient, and sustainable.

3. CHALLENGES AND CASE STUDIES

3.1 Challenges Posed by New Space Activities

The rapid proliferation of space activities, particularly the deployment of mega-constellations, presents significant challenges to the management and allocation of the radio frequency spectrum. Mega-constellations, like SpaceX's Starlink or Amazon's Project Kuiper, consist of thousands of small satellites launched into LEO. These networks are designed to provide global internet coverage but place unprecedented strain on available spectrum resources.

One major challenge is spectrum congestion. As the number of satellites operating in LEO increases, so does the potential for interference between different satellite systems and ground-based operations. Unlike terrestrial systems, satellite signals traverse vast distances and can cover entire continents, leading to overlapping frequencies and increased risk of signal disruption.¹⁵

Another challenge is the monopolization of spectrum resources. Mega-constellations are often launched by large corporations with substantial financial and political power, raising concerns about their ability to dominate spectrum allocation.¹⁶ These corporations, with their extensive funding and lobbying efforts, can secure the lion's share of available spectrum, effectively crowding out smaller players. This creates a scenario where a few dominant companies control the majority of frequency bands, leaving limited room for new or smaller entities to enter the market. Smaller nations, especially those with emerging space industries, may struggle to access these valuable resources, as they often lack the influence or financial capacity to compete for spectrum rights. As a result, the commercialization of space could become increasingly monopolized, potentially stifling innovation and limiting opportunities for developing nations or private companies without the same financial backing. This concentration of control over spectrum resources raises concerns about equity, access, and the long-term sustainability of a fair and competitive space industry.

3.2 Case Studies Highlighting the Need for Better Management

A prominent example of the challenges in spectrum management is the dispute between SpaceX's Starlink and OneWeb, both of which are vying for a share of LEO spectrum. In 2020, OneWeb filed a complaint with the FCC against SpaceX, alleging that Starlink's satellites posed a significant risk of interference to OneWeb's system.¹⁷

The complaint arose after SpaceX requested changes to its satellite operations, which OneWeb argued would bring their constellations too close to orbital altitude and frequency use. This case highlighted the difficulties in coordinating frequency usage between different satellite operators, not only in regulatory terms but also in logistical operations such as data and information sharing. It underscored the need for

¹⁵ Wheeden B. (n.d.). *Radio Frequency Spectrum, interference and satellites ...* Secure World Foundation. https://swfound.org/media/108538/swf_rfi_fact_sheet_2013.pdf

¹⁶ Office, U. S. G. A. (2022, September 29). *Large constellations of satellites: Mitigating environmental and other effects*. U.S. Government Accountability Office. <https://www.gao.gov/products/gao-22-105166>

¹⁷ Foust J. (2021, April 22). *SpaceX and OneWeb SPAR over satellite close approach*. SpaceNews. <https://spacenews.com/spacex-and-oneweb-spar-over-satellite-close-approach/>

more robust international mechanisms that facilitate seamless communication and operational coordination between stakeholders, to prevent conflicts and ensure efficient spectrum use. These mechanisms would enable operators to better align their activities, share critical data about frequency usage, and avoid operational disruptions, ultimately promoting a more collaborative and organized space environment.

While the dispute was resolved, the increasing number of similar cases points to the challenges that regulatory bodies face in managing the spectrum as space activities expand.¹⁸ Without improved coordination and more stringent regulatory frameworks, these conflicts could become more frequent, jeopardizing the safe and efficient use of the spectrum.

Another challenge arises from the impact of satellite constellations on scientific research, particularly radio astronomy. Radio astronomy relies on “quiet zones” — areas of the spectrum with minimal interference — to detect faint signals from distant celestial bodies. However, satellites emit radio signals, both intentional (for communication) and unintentional (due to electromagnetic leakage), that can overwhelm the weak signals scientists aim to capture. These emissions create “noise” that interferes with the sensitivity of radio telescopes, making it difficult for scientists to distinguish between the celestial signals and the radio interference from satellites, thereby hindering accurate and precise observations.¹⁹

This underscores the need for better management strategies that balance commercial interests with the preservation of vital scientific activities. Spectrum allocation processes must account for not only the needs of satellite operators but also the long-term sustainability of the space environment and the protection of critical scientific research.

The examples of the SpaceX-OneWeb dispute and the interference with radio astronomy illustrate the urgent need for improved spectrum management as space activities continue to grow. Regulatory frameworks must evolve to address the complexities posed by mega-constellations, ensure equitable access to spectrum, and protect scientific and environmental interests. International cooperation, stronger enforcement mechanisms, and more dynamic policy approaches will be key to navigating these challenges effectively.

4. SECURITY CONCERNS IN SPECTRUM MANAGEMENT FOR SPACE ACTIVITIES

4.1 Vulnerabilities and Threats

The integration of space activities into national security frameworks has escalated concerns regarding spectrum security. The radio frequency spectrum is not only vital for commercial satellite communications but also for strategic military and intelligence operations.²⁰ The potential for disruption or sabotage of these frequencies presents considerable security risks.

One of the primary security threats is the intentional jamming or spoofing of satellite communications. Jamming involves overpowering a satellite's frequency with noise, thereby disrupting its ability to transmit or receive data. Spoofing entails sending deceptive signals that mimic legitimate ones, leading to potential

¹⁸ Dinner J. (2022, June 21). *SpaceX and OneWeb Tell FCC their broadband megaconstellations can coexist*. Space.com. <https://www.space.com/spacex-oneweb-satellite-internet-constellation-coexistence>

¹⁹ *Radio Frequency Interference*. National Radio Astronomy Observatory. (2019, April 24). <https://public.nrao.edu/telescopes/radio-frequency-interference/>

²⁰ *The invisible force powering our world*. Lockheed Martin. (2024, February 13). <https://www.lockheedmartin.com/en-us/news/features/2024/the-invisible-force-powering-our-world.html#:~:text=The%20U.S.%20and%20its%20allies,to%20see%20or%20locate%20them>

miscommunication or data redirection. These tactics can severely impact military operations and critical infrastructure, highlighting the need for advanced protective measures and response strategies.²¹

The cybersecurity of satellite systems and ground stations is increasingly under threat from cyberattacks. Unauthorized access to these systems can compromise sensitive information, disrupt operations, or even gain control over satellite functionalities.²² As space-based assets become more integral to national security, the protection of these systems from cyber threats must be a priority.

4.2 Strategic Spectrum Usage

The strategic importance of certain frequency bands used for military and defense purposes underscores the need for secure spectrum management. The competition for these bands among various national and commercial entities has heightened security concerns.

The development of advanced military satellites and space capabilities by various nations introduces additional security risks. Geopolitical rivalries and the potential for aggressive spectrum use by some countries can lead to interference or conflicts over spectrum access. This situation necessitates stronger international cooperation and regulation to ensure that spectrum usage does not compromise global security.²³

4.3 Dual-Use Technology and Ethical Implications

The dual-use nature of many commercial satellites, serving both civilian and military functions, adds another layer of complexity to spectrum management. As satellite operators navigate the increasingly crowded frequency bands, they must also contend with the security concerns associated with these dual-use technologies. Satellites providing critical civilian services, such as broadband internet, may also be used for military reconnaissance or communications. This overlap raises ethical and legal issues, particularly in times of conflict, where such satellites may become strategic targets.²⁴ The potential for these satellites to be disabled or destroyed during a conflict, while temporarily serving military objectives, raises serious concerns regarding the disruption of vital civilian services. This tension between security needs and humanitarian impact underscores the broader challenge of balancing competing demands for spectrum.

Moreover, the targeting of dual-use satellites during military conflicts can result in substantial collateral damage, potentially impacting essential civilian infrastructure.²⁵ Given the growing reliance on satellites for both civilian and defense purposes, it becomes critical that legal frameworks governing spectrum management address not only the technical and operational aspects but also the ethical ramifications. These frameworks must ensure that both military and civilian interests are adequately protected, promoting a balance between security concerns and the uninterrupted functioning of global communication networks.

4.4 Regulatory and Policy Challenges

The current regulatory frameworks for spectrum management may not fully address the security challenges posed by the evolving space environment.

²¹ Velkovsky P, Mohan J, & Simon M. (2019, April 3). *Satellite jamming*. On the Radar. <https://ontheradar.csis.org/issue-briefs/satellite-jamming/>

²² Office, U. S. G. A. (2024, May 1). *NASA cybersecurity: Plan needed to update spacecraft acquisition policies and standards*. U.S. Government Accountability Office. <https://www.gao.gov/products/gao-24-106624>

²³ Erwin, S. (2023, March 15). *Space force: We expect to see “interfering, blinding” of satellites during conflict*. SpaceNews. <https://spacenews.com/space-force-we-expect-to-see-interfering-blinding-of-satellites-during-conflict/>

²⁴ Bingen, K. A., Johnson, K., & Smith, Z. M. (2022, November 10). *Russia threatens to target commercial satellites*. CSIS. <https://www.csis.org/analysis/russia-threatens-target-commercial-satellites>

²⁵ *Ibid.*

Existing international treaties, such as the OST, were established during a time when the scope and scale of space activities were far less expensive and technologically advanced. As a result, they do not fully account for the security complexities of modern spectrum management, particularly in the context of militarized space operations. These treaties were not designed to address the increased risks of hostile interference or the growing competition for limited spectrum resources, both of which are heightened by the proliferation of commercial and military satellites. In this new space era, the existing frameworks need to be adapted or supplemented with new agreements that more specifically tackle these emerging security concerns. Updated legal frameworks should focus on preventing hostile interference, managing the competition for spectrum resources, and ensuring that both military and civilian systems are adequately protected in an increasingly crowded and contested space environment.²⁶

Effective management of spectrum security requires enhanced international cooperation and more robust enforcement mechanisms. Governments and international organizations must work together to develop and implement policies that address the security risks associated with spectrum use. This includes establishing dedicated channels for intergovernmental communication during satellite interference incidents, creating joint protocols for identifying and attributing malicious interference, and strengthening the role of institutions like the ITU in mediating disputes. Additionally, regional security alliances and space-focused forums could develop shared frameworks for managing dual-use technologies and responding to threats in a coordinated, transparent manner.

As space activities and technologies continue to advance, the security concerns related to spectrum management will become more pronounced. Addressing these concerns requires a comprehensive approach that includes technological innovations, international cooperation, and updated regulatory frameworks. By prioritizing security and developing effective strategies to manage spectrum resources, the international community can ensure the stability and reliability of space-based operations while mitigating potential risks.

5. ENVIRONMENTAL SUSTAINABILITY IN SPECTRUM MANAGEMENT FOR SPACE ACTIVITIES

5.1 Environmental Impact of Satellite Operations

The increasing number of satellites and mega-constellations in LEO presents significant environmental sustainability challenges, impacting both the space and Earth environments.

Space Debris: One of the most pressing environmental concerns arising from satellite operations is the growing issue of space debris. The increasing density of satellites, especially in large constellations, heightens the risk of collisions, which can generate debris that endangers both operational satellites and future space missions.²⁷ This debris poses an additional regulatory challenge in spectrum management, as debris can interfere with satellite communication and navigation systems, complicating frequency coordination. Furthermore, the threat of cascading collisions, known as the "Kessler Syndrome," exacerbates this issue, leading to a greater need for global agreements on debris mitigation strategies as part of spectrum management.²⁸

²⁶ *National Spectrum Strategy - November 2023*. NTIA. (2023, November 13). https://www.ntia.gov/sites/default/files/publications/national_spectrum_strategy_final.pdf

²⁷ *About space debris*. ESA. (n.d.). https://www.esa.int/Space_Safety/Space_Debris/About_space_debris

²⁸ Kelvey, J. (2024, March 8). *Understanding the misunderstood Kessler syndrome*. University of Arizona Space4 Center. <https://s4.arizona.edu/news/understanding-misunderstood-kessler-syndrome#:~:text=Kessler%20Syndrome%20is%20a%20nightmare,%2C%20in%20turn%2C%20cascading%20collisions>

Light Pollution: Satellites, particularly those in large constellations, also contribute to light pollution, which impacts both the Earth's environment and scientific research. The brightness of these satellites obstructs the natural night sky, interfering with astronomical observations and disrupting the natural environment for wildlife and humans. This pollution not only affects scientific endeavors that rely on radio frequencies for observation but also increases public concern over the long-term sustainability of space activities. As more satellites occupy space, regulators face the challenge of balancing spectrum demands with environmental protection, ensuring that spectrum management practices also consider the preservation of dark skies for research and ecosystem health.²⁹

The environmental implications of satellite operations present a complex layer to the broader debate on spectrum management. As space activities expand, it is crucial for international regulatory frameworks to evolve in a way that balances the growth of space technologies with the protection of both the space environment and Earth's ecosystems. Spectrum management policies must consider the environmental impact, ensuring that the demands of commercial space activities do not overshadow the need for environmental sustainability.

5.2 International and National Efforts

As the demand for radio spectrum increases with the growth of satellite constellations and space activities, both international and national initiatives have been established to promote environmental sustainability in space, with a specific focus on managing the impacts on the space environment and ensuring the continued effectiveness of spectrum use. Space debris and light pollution are not only environmental concerns but also directly affect the availability and reliability of the radio spectrum used by satellites.

International organizations such as the Inter-Agency Space Debris Coordination Committee (IADC) and the United Nations Office for Outer Space Affairs (UNOOSA) provide guidelines for mitigating space debris, which in turn impacts the management of radio frequencies.³⁰ Space debris can interfere with operational satellites, disrupting communication signals and increasing the risk of signal interference in already crowded frequency bands. By establishing best practices for satellite design, operation, and end-of-life disposal, these organizations aim to reduce the risk of debris-related interference, ensuring that radio frequencies remain available for active use.

On the national level, countries have enacted regulations to address both space debris and light pollution, which also have implications for spectrum management. For example, in the United States, the Federal Communications Commission (FCC) requires satellite operators to submit detailed end-of-life plans and debris mitigation strategies as part of their licensing process.³¹ This regulation is aimed at ensuring that satellites do not contribute to the growing debris problem, which could cause operational disruptions to other satellites relying on the same radio frequencies. By incorporating these environmental considerations into the regulatory process, nations can better manage the balance between satellite operations and the preservation of a sustainable, interference-free spectrum.

²⁹ The Trustees of Princeton University. (n.d.). *Light pollution from satellites*. Princeton University. <https://www.astro.princeton.edu/~gbakos/satellites/>

³⁰ IADC *Space Debris Mitigation Guidelines*. NASA. (n.d.). <https://orbitaldebris.jsc.nasa.gov/library/iadc-space-debris-guidelines-revision-2.pdf>

³¹ *FCC adopts new "5-year rule" for deorbiting satellites*. Federal Communications Commission. (2022, September 29). <https://www.fcc.gov/document/fcc-adopts-new-5-year-rule-deorbiting-satellites>

Efforts at both international and national levels are critical in ensuring that space activities, including the use of the radio spectrum, are conducted in an environmentally responsible manner. These initiatives not only help mitigate space debris and light pollution but also support the continued availability and reliability of the radio spectrum, which is essential for both commercial and scientific satellite communications.

5.3 Balancing Technological Advancement with Environmental Concerns

As space activities grow, it is essential to balance technological advancements with environmental sustainability, particularly in the context of radio spectrum management. The rapid development of space technologies, including satellite constellations, must consider not only the benefits they provide but also their potential environmental impact. The expansion of satellite networks increases the demand for available frequencies, but it also raises concerns about space debris and light pollution, which directly affect the usability of the radio spectrum.

Encouraging the development of technologies that minimize the environmental footprint of space activities is crucial to maintaining the sustainability of both space and the radio spectrum. This includes investing in more efficient satellite designs, exploring alternative propulsion systems, and using environmentally friendly materials that reduce the risk of generating debris or contributing to light pollution. Additionally, satellite designs should incorporate features that prevent interference with existing spectrum allocations, ensuring that technological advancements do not compromise the effectiveness or reliability of communication networks.

Integrating environmental sustainability into space policy and regulatory frameworks is essential to ensure that future activities consider their impact on the environment and the radio spectrum. Policies should promote sustainable practices, incentivize the adoption of eco-friendly technologies, and address the potential for new technologies to impact spectrum access. This can be achieved by including environmental criteria in satellite licensing processes, such as debris mitigation plans, and by prioritizing research into low-impact technologies.

Environmental sustainability plays a crucial role in spectrum management for space activities. Addressing challenges like space debris, light pollution, and sustainable spectrum use requires a coordinated approach involving international guidelines, national regulations, and technological innovation. By ensuring that space industry growth prioritizes environmental considerations, the industry can help preserve a stable and interference-free radio spectrum for future generations while minimizing its impact on both space and Earth environments.

6. POSSIBLE SOLUTIONS FOR SPECTRUM MANAGEMENT CHALLENGES

6.1 Technological Innovations

Advancements in technology offer potential solutions for addressing spectrum management challenges in space. Implementing frequency reuse techniques can optimize spectrum use. By using the same frequency bands for different satellite systems in separate space or time segments, spectrum efficiency can be increased. Enhanced signal processing technologies can mitigate interference issues. Techniques such as beamforming, adaptive filtering, and interference cancellation improve clarity and reliability, reducing the impact of overlapping frequencies. For example, beamforming allows satellite antennas to direct signals precisely toward ground stations, which helps avoid interference with nearby users. Adaptive filtering enables systems to adjust to changing noise conditions in real time. Interference cancellation works by identifying and subtracting unwanted signals, such as those from other satellites, to improve the overall quality of communication. Developing advanced space traffic management systems improves coordination and reduces collision risk. These systems can provide real-time tracking of satellites and debris, helping operators avoid conflicts and manage spectrum resources more effectively.

6.2 Policy and Regulatory Improvements

Updating and strengthening policy and regulatory frameworks is essential for managing spectrum challenges. Enhancing international cooperation is crucial for managing the growing demand for spectrum. Multilateral agreements and collaborative frameworks can help harmonize spectrum allocation and coordinate frequency band use across countries and commercial entities.³² Updating regulatory frameworks to address the challenges posed by mega-constellations and emerging technologies is essential. Reforms should focus on ensuring equitable spectrum access, managing disputes, and protecting scientific and environmental interests.³³

6.3 Enhanced Coordination and Enforcement

Effective spectrum management requires robust coordination and enforcement mechanisms. Establishing effective conflict resolution mechanisms helps address disputes between satellite operators and manage spectrum conflicts. Processes for negotiation, arbitration, and adjudication are necessary for resolving spectrum allocation and interference issues. Improving monitoring and compliance measures ensures adherence to spectrum regulations and mitigation strategies. Regular audits, reporting requirements, and penalties for non-compliance can help enforce policies and maintain order.³⁴ Collaborating with private entities can enhance spectrum management efforts. Public-private partnerships facilitate new technology development, share best practices, and support sustainable management solutions.

Addressing spectrum management challenges in space requires a multifaceted approach that includes technological innovations, policy improvements, and enhanced coordination. By leveraging advancements in technology, updating regulatory frameworks, and fostering international cooperation, the space community can effectively manage spectrum resources and ensure the sustainability of space activities. Environmental sustainability remains a crucial aspect of spectrum management, as the use and regulation of radio frequencies directly intersect with both the space and Earth environments. Unregulated or poorly coordinated spectrum use can contribute to increased satellite congestion, rising collision risks, and electromagnetic interference, all of which have environmental consequences. For instance, crowded radio bands can lead to operational inefficiencies, prompting the launch of additional satellites and thus exacerbating space debris issues. Similarly, the proliferation of satellites emitting radio waves and light pollution can disrupt scientific research and natural ecosystems.

Balancing technological progress with environmental responsibility means developing sustainable spectrum strategies that limit harmful interference, reduce overpopulation in orbit, and encourage the design of satellites that are mindful of both terrestrial and astronomical environments. Through coordinated international and national efforts, the space industry can promote sustainable growth while minimizing its environmental impact.

7. CONCLUSION

As space activities advance at an unprecedented pace, effective spectrum management has become crucial. This paper has explored the multifaceted challenges associated with managing radio frequencies in the era of mega-constellations, emphasizing the need for robust frameworks to address interference, security, and environmental concerns.

³² *The future of the ITU WRC cycle: Keeping pace with technological progress*. Access Partnership. (2024, January 15). <https://accesspartnership.com/future-of-itu-wrc-cycle/>

³³ *Strategic framework for space diplomacy*. U.S. Department of State. (n.d.). <https://www.state.gov/wp-content/uploads/2023/05/Space-Framework-Clean-2-May-2023-Final-Updated-Accessible-5.25.2023.pdf>

³⁴ *Ibid.*

The rise of large satellite constellations has created significant congestion in the radio frequency spectrum, leading to potential conflicts and disruptions in communications. Disputes like those between SpaceX and OneWeb, along with interference with radio astronomy, illustrate the urgent need for enhanced coordination and regulatory mechanisms to manage spectrum resources effectively. The risks of jamming, spoofing, and cyberattacks highlight the vulnerabilities in satellite communications that must be addressed through updated international agreements and stronger cooperative efforts. Ensuring the protection of both military and civilian systems is essential for maintaining the stability of space operations. The growth of space debris and light pollution impacts both space and Earth environments, underscoring the importance of incorporating sustainable practices into spectrum management. Efforts from international bodies and national regulators are crucial, but a balanced approach that considers technological advancement alongside environmental protection is necessary. Managing spectrum in the expanding realm of space activities requires a holistic approach that integrates technological innovation, policy improvements, and international cooperation. By addressing the operational, security, and environmental challenges, and fostering effective solutions, the space industry can ensure the sustainable use of spectrum resources and maintain the integrity of both space and Earth environments. This integrated approach will be key to navigating the future of space communications and preserving the delicate balance of our shared space environment.

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Investigating Orbital Debris Mitigation Regime Development In the United States

Kaili Ayers¹

ABSTRACT

This article examines the orbital debris mitigation regimes administered by the Federal Communications Commission (FCC), the Federal Aviation Administration (FAA) and the National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA). It explores the statutory foundations that empower each agency's regulatory authority and assesses how their respective mission-authorisation processes address or exacerbate gaps in the United States' approach to debris management. The current fragmented framework, spread across multiple agencies with overlapping jurisdictions, has created inefficiencies and regulatory blind spots, undermining effective mitigation as space becomes increasingly congested. While the FCC has updated its licensing requirements and the FAA and NOAA have proposed targeted rules on launch-vehicle disposal and remote-sensing activities, respectively, these measures remain piecemeal. The article argues that a unified, streamlined mission-authorisation framework, aligned with international best practice and treaty obligations, is essential to ensure regulatory clarity, foster interagency collaboration, and incentivise innovation. By prioritising a cohesive debris-mitigation regime, the United States can safeguard orbital sustainability and maintain its leadership in the global space economy.

KEYWORDS: orbital debris, regulatory fragmentation, mission authorisation, interagency coordination, space sustainability

1. INTRODUCTION: THE PROBLEM OF ORBITAL DEBRIS

The commercial space industry is expanding at a rapid pace, driven by innovative technological developments and a thriving economic environment. McKinsey & Company estimates that the global space economy will be worth \$1.8 trillion by 2035, up from \$630 billion in 2023.² This growth is exciting for the future of the commercial space industry, but it also brings a significant challenge: the rapid proliferation of orbital debris in outer space. This poses challenges for the sustainable use of our final frontier by endangering both operational space systems and humans in orbit, creating interference in the collection of vital data, and increasing situations that present risks to national security. As this risk grows, it is timely and of great importance to examine how regulatory bodies administer policies and laws to mitigate such risks in order to foster a sustainable outer space environment for present and future generations. However,

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² McKinsey & Company. (2024, April 8). Space: The \$1.8 trillion opportunity for global economic growth, para 1. <https://www.mckinsey.com/industries/aerospace-and-defense/our-insights/space-the-1-point-8-trillion-dollar-opportunity-for-global-economic-growth>

the regulatory framework for orbital debris mitigation in the United States is fragmented across multiple federal agencies, which creates an inefficient regulatory environment that not only obstructs the growth of the commercial space industry in the U.S. but also incentivizes foreign companies to take their business elsewhere.

This article seeks to explore the orbital debris mitigation regimes of the Federal Communications Commission (FCC), the Federal Aviation Administration (FAA), and the National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA). Specifically, it examines the statutory authorities underpinning each agency's regulatory powers and, in doing so, aims to forecast the trajectory of the United States' orbital debris mitigation regime and provide commentary on mission authorization as a crucial measure to address these regulatory gaps in the United States.

1.1 Orbital Debris 101

Orbital debris are a result of collisions between various space objects, including non-functional satellites, spent rocket stages, as well as fragments from collisions or disintegration. The Kessler Syndrome, first proposed by NASA scientist Donald Kessler (and co-authored by Burton Cour-Palais), describes a cascading effect where debris collisions generate even more debris, exponentially increasing the risk to operational spacecraft.³ Kessler and Courpalais' seminal 1978 work noted that this upward trend of collisions could hinder humanity's future space ambitions and activities, even predicting that satellite collisions would become a source of space junk by the year 2000, if not sooner.⁴ This debris endangers operational space systems, interferes with the collection of vital data, and presents risks to national security. According to the Aerospace Corporation, "[a] piece of space debris the size of a blueberry can create the impact of a falling anvil."⁵ This has tremendous implications for establishing a long-term, sustainable presence in low earth orbit (LEO) and beyond. Astronauts aboard the International Space Station (ISS), for example, had to perform multiple orbital maneuvers to avoid debris collisions that reach speeds of up to 22,000 miles per hour. In March 2023, ISS astronauts were forced to fire thrusters twice within an eight-day period to avoid projected collisions, and in the previous year, the ISS maneuvered three times to avoid high-probability collisions, which were a result from the 2020 breakup of a Russian Fregat upper stage tank.⁶ For context, between 1999-2011, the mean amount of times the ISS was forced to maneuver to avoid a collision an average of once per year. However, between 2012-2024 the mean increased to 2.25, representing more than double the number of avoidance maneuvers that occurred within the last twelve years.⁷

These incidents highlight the urgent need for robust regulatory frameworks, ensuring not only safety for current operations, but also the long-term viability of future space activities. With the increasing threat of permanent harm to both space infrastructure and humans in orbit, governments should aim to promulgate

³ Wall, M. (2022, July 14). Kessler Syndrome and the space debris problem. Space.com, para 6. <https://www.space.com/kessler-syndrome-space-debris>

⁴ *Ibid.*

⁵ Aerospace Corporation. (n.d.). *Space debris 101*. Retrieved from <https://aerospace.org/article/space-debris-101>

⁶ *National Aeronautics and Space Administration*. (2023, June). *Orbital Debris Quarterly News* (p. 2). NASA Orbital Debris Program Office. <https://orbitaldebris.jsc.nasa.gov/quarterly-news/pdfs/odqnv27i2.pdf>

⁷ Note that between the years 2004-2007, 2013, and 2016-2019, there were either no reported data points or there were zero avoidance measures taken. See, Pare, S. (2024, November 26). *ISS dodges its 39th piece of potentially hazardous space junk*. LiveScience. <https://www.livescience.com/space/space-exploration/iss-dodges-its-39th-piece-of-potentially-hazardous-space-junk-experts-say-it-wont-be-the-last>

regulations that not only reduce the current volume of debris, but also places limits on future debris generation.

2. REGULATORY OVERLAP

The United States' regulatory framework for orbital debris is spread across multiple federal agencies, leading to the issue of overlapping jurisdictions and potential inefficiencies that hinder the fluid development of the commercial space industry. The White House, the National Space Council, and the Senate Commerce Committee have all proposed mission authorization frameworks to fill regulatory gaps and streamline oversight. However, the current system ultimately remains fragmented. The FCC has positioned itself as taking the lead in orbital debris mitigation regulation for operational satellite telecommunications, while other federal agencies contribute in other specialized areas: the FAA regulates launch and reentry, NOAA oversees private remote sensing, and NASA provides policy recommendations and guidelines grounded in science.

3. FCC ORBITAL DEBRIS MITIGATION FRAMEWORK

The FCC's involvement in orbital debris mitigation stems from its broader mandate to regulate communications. The *Communications Satellite Act of 1962*⁸ established the FCC's authority over satellite communications, providing a foundation for its role in orbital debris mitigation.⁹ The FCC's statutory authority is grounded in its ability to license satellite operators and ensure compliance with technical and operational standards.

In 2004, the FCC concluded that Section 307(a) of the Communications Act, which mandates licensing radio communications in the "public convenience, interest, or necessity," granted it sufficient authority to adopt orbital debris mitigation requirements.¹⁰ The FCC's interpretation of 307(a) centers around the fact that its orbital debris mitigation rules would serve to advance the Communications Act because orbital debris as a phenomenon affects the cost, reliability, continuity, and safety of satellite operations and the services they provide. Furthermore, broadening the scope of its de facto jurisdictional authority would enable the FCC to promote the effective use of radio in the public interest as per its statutory mandate.¹¹ Thus, the FCC's interpretation of Section 307(a) indicates that its licensing framework for communication satellite activities necessarily should address debris control and prevention.¹²

Building on this interpretation, the FCC proactively took measures to advance orbital debris rulemaking in 2020 and again in 2022 by releasing updated rules to address orbital debris explicitly.¹³ The 2020 rules require satellite operators to submit debris mitigation plans as part of their licensing applications, and the

⁸ Satellite Communications Act of 1962, Pub. L. No. 87-624, 76 Stat. 419 (codified as amended in scattered sections of 47 U.S.C.).

⁹ Harbert, M., & Balakrishnan, A. (2023, Summer). Why space debris flies through regulatory gaps. *Issues in Science and Technology*, para. 3. <https://issues.org/space-debris-fcc-harbert-balakrishnan/#0>

¹⁰ Brown, L., & Stimers, P. (2023, November 6). The FCC's authority in regulating orbital debris. *The Space Review*, para 7. <https://www.thespacereview.com/article/4687/1>

¹¹ Kensinger, K., Duall, S., & Persaud, S. (2005, April 18–20). The United States Federal Communications Commission's regulations concerning mitigation of orbital debris. In D. Danesy (Ed.), *Proceedings of the 4th European Conference on Space Debris* (ESA SP-587, p. 571). ESA/ESOC. <https://adsabs.harvard.edu/full/2005ESASP.587..571K>

¹² U.S. Congress, Office of Technology Assessment, *Orbiting Debris: A Space Environmental Problem-Background Paper*, OTA-BP-ISC-72 (Washington, DC: U.S. Government Printing Office, September 1990), Appendix C. <https://ota.fas.org/reports/9033.pdf>

¹³ *Supra* note 10, para. 9.

updated 2022 rules require satellites ending their mission in or passing through Low Earth Orbit (LEO) to deorbit as soon as is practical and no more than five years following mission completion—a significant reduction from the previous post-mission deorbiting guideline of 25 years.¹⁴

Since the FCC exercises oversight over the operation of telecommunications satellites, and since most satellites require part of the radio spectrum to transmit data and information from space, the FCC has effectively become the *de facto* debris regulator for satellite operators.¹⁵ However, despite the agency's proactive measures to address orbital debris, its approach and use of such authority has thus far sparked controversy. While its updated rules provide a framework for debris mitigation, critics argue that the FCC's actions exceed its statutory authority because it has been unilaterally adjudicating regulations on this topic. While a broad jurisdictional authority allows the FCC to act quickly, critics view such actions as conflicting with broader administration policies, lacking coordination with other agencies, or acting presumptively ahead of a coordinated administration position.¹⁶

The FCC's *de facto* authority has been established over time through various rulemaking and case determinations with orbital debris as the core issue. In 2022, for example, the U.S. appeals court (D.C. Cir) denied ViaSat's attempt to force an environmental review on SpaceX based on the statutory requirements of the National Environmental Policy Act (NEPA).¹⁷ It should be noted here that the court denied ViaSat's appeal based on Article III standing requirements, not on the merits of its NEPA argument. However, in the context of NEPA, it will be interesting to see how opponents of the FCC's regulatory framework for orbital debris exploit NEPA's environmental review requirements as a sword against regulating agencies since it requires federal agencies to consider the environmental impact of their actions before making decisions. While the application of NEPA has never been used in the context of outer space thus far, entities may turn to it in light of the proliferation of orbital debris. Whether NEPA applies to the outer space environment is, however, a question this article does not address.¹⁸

Subsequently, in 2023, the FCC took its first space debris enforcement action against DISH for failing to move its EchoStar-7 satellite to the proper disposal orbit at the satellite's end-of-life as required by DISH's license terms and conditions, further underscoring its *de facto* authority in this domain.¹⁹ Despite these rulings, the recent *Loper Bright Enterprises v. Raimondo* case struck down the Chevron deference and effectively ended federal agencies' ability to interpret ambiguities in the laws they enforced with greater latitude. In the aftermath of the *Loper Bright* decision, it is now of the utmost importance that the regulatory ambiguity and overlap amongst federal agencies be resolved so as to ensure a clear and cohesive framework for addressing orbital debris going forward.

¹⁴ *Ibid.*

¹⁵ *Supra* note 9, para. 16.

¹⁶ *Ibid.*

¹⁷ Rainbow, J. (2024, September 16). Connecting the dots: FCC's space sustainability authority in question as need grows. SpaceNews, para 7. <https://spacenews.com/connecting-the-dots-fcc-space-sustainability-authority-question-need-grows/>

¹⁸ *A Sky Full of Stars: Should ViaSat, Inc. v. FCC. Change the Agency's Treatment of Satellites as a Categorical Exclusion Under the National Environmental Policy Act* by Morgan Armstrong.

¹⁹ Federal Communications Commission. (2023, October 2). In the matter of DISH Operating L.L.C. (DA 23-888). <https://docs.fcc.gov/public/attachments/DA-23-888A1.pdf>

4. FAA'S ORBITAL DEBRIS MITIGATION FRAMEWORK

The FAA, under the Department of Transportation (DOT), licenses commercial launch and reentry vehicles, as well as commercial spaceports.²⁰ In 1984, the Office of Commercial Space Transportation (AST) was established as a part of the DOT and in 1995, it was subsequently integrated into the FAA as its only space related line of business.²¹ The FAA addresses orbital debris in commercial space launch activities through licensing and enforcement, research and standards development, and setting financial responsibility and risk allocation requirements.²²

Its authority for regulating orbital debris is derived from the Commercial Space Launch Act of 1984, as codified and amended at 51 U.S.C., which specifically authorizes the Department of Transportation, and consequently, the FAA, “to oversee, license, and regulate commercial launch and reentry activities, and the operation of launch and reentry sites as carried out by the United States (U.S.) citizens or within the United States.”²³ In terms of its mission review process and launch license application evaluation, the FAA examines each proposed commercial launch to ensure that no other activities occurring in space are directly at risk. Furthermore, an interagency review of the application, including input from NASA and the Department of Defence (DOD), assists in this process.²⁴

Over the years, the FAA has developed regulations that seek to mitigate the threat posed by orbital debris in several ways. In 14 C.F.R. Part 415.39, the FAA requires expendable launch vehicle (ELV) launch license applicants to demonstrate compliance with §417.129 for any proposed launch of a launch vehicle with a stage or component that will reach Earth orbit. §417.129²⁵ requires applicants to demonstrate that: (1) there is no unplanned physical contact between the vehicle or any of its components and the payload after payload separation; (2) debris generation does not result from the conversion of energy sources into energy that fragments the vehicle or its components, and (3) for all vehicle stages or components that are left in orbit, stored energy is removed by depleting residual fuel and leaving all fuel line valves open, venting any pressurized system, leaving all batteries in a permanent discharge state, and removing any remaining source of stored energy.²⁶ In addition to Part 415.39, 14 C.F.R Part 431.43 specifies that the first two requirements of §417.129 apply to reusable launch and reentry vehicles, and further requires a reusable vehicle operator to perform a collision avoidance analysis to ensure a 200-kilometer separation between the vehicle and an inhabitable orbiting object during launch and reentry.²⁷ Lastly, 14 C.F.R. Part 440, Appendix A, requires launch license applicants seeking a maximum probable loss determination for their activities to share with the FAA, an analysis of the risks posed by launch vehicles to operational satellites in orbit.²⁸

In September of 2023, the FAA released a Notice of Proposed Rulemaking (NPRM) to mitigate the risk posed to the public by uncontrolled disposals, which are situations where satellites reenter Earth's

²⁰ *Commercial Space: Federal Regulation, Oversight, and Utilization*, Congressional Research Service, November 29, 2018, pg. 1. <https://sgp.fas.org/crs/space/R45416.pdf>

²¹ Federal Aviation Administration. (2025, March 20). *About the Office of Commercial Space Transportation*, para 1. https://www.faa.gov/about/office_org/headquarters_offices/ast

²² *U.S. Congress, Office of Technology Assessment, Orbiting Debris: A Space Environmental Problem-Background Paper, OTA-BP-ISC-72* (Washington, DC: U.S. Government Printing Office, September 1990), Appendix C.

²³ Mitigation Methods for Launch Vehicle Upper Stages on the Creation of Orbital Debris, 88 Fed. Reg. 65835 (proposed Sept. 26, 2023) (to be codified at 14 C.F.R. pts. 401, 404, 415, 417, 431, 43, 437, 450, 453).

²⁴ *U.S. Congress, Office of Technology Assessment, Orbiting Debris: A Space Environmental Problem-Background Paper, OTA-BP-ISC-72* (Washington, DC: U.S. Government Printing Office, September 1990), Appendix C.

²⁵ Note that 14 C.F.R. Part 450, §450.171 lists the same requirements as §417.129.

²⁶ 14 C.F.R. § 417.129 (2006).

²⁷ Federal Aviation Administration. (2002). Launch Activity and Orbital Debris Mitigation: Second Quarter 2002 Quarterly Launch Report (p. 11). https://www.faa.gov/about/office_org/headquarters_offices/ast/media/q22002.pdf

²⁸ *Id.*

atmosphere without using propulsion to control its descent.²⁹ The FAA's proposed regulations would require commercial launch providers to dispose of upper stages from their launches in an effort to mitigate the growth of orbital debris.³⁰ Specifically, in the NPRM, the FAA asserted that operators could meet this requirement by performing one of five disposal options that must be performed within 30 days of mission completion: (1) controlled disposal, (2) maneuver to a disposal orbit, (3) maneuver to an Earth-escape orbit, (4) retrieve the debris within 5 years of mission completion, or (5) perform atmospheric uncontrolled disposal or natural decay within 25 years.³¹ As of April 2025, the FAA has not yet issued a final rule, but plans to finalize and publish it sometime in 2025.³²

5. NOAA APPROACH TO ORBITAL DEBRIS MITIGATION

NOAA's role in orbital debris mitigation is linked to its broader mandate to regulate remote sensing. The National and Commercial Space Programs Act (51 U.S.C. Subtitle VI)³³ provides NOAA with explicit statutory authority to oversee commercial remote sensing activities. Under 51 U.S. Code § 60121, NOAA regulates the operation of commercial remote sensing satellites and consequently, maintains the indirect statutory authority to promulgate debris mitigation regulations. § 60121(b) mandates that NOAA comply with any applicable international obligations and national security concerns of the United States. Effectively, this means that NOAA, in regulating commercial remote sensing, must comply with the U.S.'s obligations as outlined in the OST and the Liability Convention.

NOAA's jurisdiction is further limited by 15 CFR Part 960. For example, §960.2(b) states: "a system that contains only such instruments³⁴ will not require a Commerce license," and effectively excludes those instruments used primarily for mission assurance or other technical purposes from NOAA's oversight.³⁵ NOAA's existing statutory authority has led to debates about the agency's future role in orbital debris mitigation and the need for expanded authority, which is particularly consequential in the context of a booming international commercial satellite industry and the need for the U.S. to maintain an attractive regulatory environment for both domestic and foreign satellite companies. Indeed, a recent Center for Strategic and International Studies (CSIS) publication noted that "providing regulatory clarity and certainty through a comprehensive mission authorization framework will encourage increased investment and innovation in space."³⁶

5.1 Policy Developments and Challenges

NOAA's role in orbital debris mitigation has evolved alongside the growth of the commercial space industry. The agency has continued to align its regulations with broader national policies, such as NASA's Orbital Debris Mitigation Standard Practices (ODMSP) and the Inter-Agency Space Debris Coordination

²⁹ Mitigation Methods *supra* note 41.

³⁰ Foust, J. (2023, September 21). *FAA proposes rule to limit lifetime of upper stages in orbit*. SpaceNews. <https://spacenews.com/faa-proposes-rule-to-limit-lifetime-of-upper-stages-in-orbit/>

³¹ Mitigation Methods *supra* note 41.

³² Foust, J. (2024, September 8). *FAA to complete orbital debris upper stage regulations in 2025*. SpaceNews. <https://spacenews.com/faa-to-complete-orbital-debris-upper-stage-regulations-in-2025/>

³³ National and Commercial Space Programs Act, Pub. L. No. 111-314, 124 Stat. 3328 (2010).

³⁴ "Instruments" are defined as: [those] used primarily for mission assurance purposes or other technical purposes are not considered remote sensing instruments under this final rule.

³⁵ National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration, Commercial Remote Sensing Regulatory Affairs. (2022, April 1). *Policy Guidance: Mission assurance (Guidance Circular No. 960.2-1)*. https://www.space.commerce.gov/wp-content/uploads/Guidance_-_Mission-Assurance-040122.pdf

³⁶ Swope, C. (2023, December 20). *Mission authorization: Decoding the space policy dilemma*. CSIS, para 12. <https://www.csis.org/analysis/mission-authorization-decoding-space-policy-dilemma>

Committee (IADC)³⁷ guidelines. However, its limited statutory authority to private remote sensing has curbed its ability to address the full spectrum of debris mitigation challenges.

Early on, the Commercial Remote Sensing Regulatory Affairs (CRSRA) made concerted efforts to develop orbital debris mitigation regulations. From 2000 to 2020, CRSRA (pronounced *kris-rah*) required companies applying for a private remote sensing license to submit a disposal and orbital debris mitigation plan; however after updating its regulations in 2020, that requirement was subsequently eliminated.³⁸ Instead, CRSRA decided to defer to FCC license requirements for orbital debris and spacecraft disposal in order to avoid duplicative regulation.³⁹ Subsequently, in 2024, it began soliciting public comments regarding potential new instructions on the disposal of on-orbit satellites with the purpose of mitigating orbital debris pertaining to subsection (b)(4)'s license requirement of the Land Remote Sensing Act of 1992 (e.g. 51 U.S.C. chapter 601).⁴⁰ Specifically, CRSRA sought "information from interested parties regarding the condition in every CRSRA license requiring the disposal of on orbit spacecraft in a matter satisfactory to the President," and that such information was "necessary to inform CRSRA's approach to providing additional guidance or initiating a narrow rulemaking pertaining to its disposal condition."⁴¹

A growing challenge that CRSRA has seen in recent years is the increasing number of multinational providers of remote sensing systems choosing to obtain radiofrequency licenses from other countries while simultaneously seeking a private remote sensing license in the U.S.⁴² An overarching question to this trend is whether these foreign licenses are sufficiently meeting U.S. standards of orbital debris mitigation. It is important to note that the U.S.'s standard is tied to its international obligations under the 1967 Treaty on Principles Governing the Activities of States in the Exploration and Use of Outer Space, including the Moon and Other Celestial Bodies (OST), requires state parties to the treaty maintain an authorization and supervision (regulatory) framework.⁴³ This means that it is effectively a state's responsibility to both provide authorization for its commercial space activities and subsequently regulate them, including any regulation of orbital debris. Specifically, a state must bear responsibility for damages to other member states resulting from national space activities.⁴⁴ However, the fragmented nature of U.S. regulatory authority has made it difficult to ensure comprehensive oversight of these obligations in practice.

³⁷ The IADC Guidelines are developed and maintained by the IADC, an international forum of space agencies and authorized governmental or intergovernmental entities to "exchange information on space debris research activities between member space agencies, to facilitate opportunities for co-operation in space debris research, to review the progress of ongoing co-operative activities and to identify debris mitigation options." The most recent update to these guidelines was published in January 2025. *See Comm. on the Peaceful Uses of Outer Space, Sci. & Tech. Subcomm., IADC Space Debris Mitigation Guidelines, U.N. Doc. A/AC.105/C.1/2025/CRP.9 (Feb. 3, 2025)*. https://www.unoosa.org/res/oosadoc/data/documents/2025/aac_105c_12025crp/aac_105c_12025crp_9_0_html/AC_105_C1_2025_CRP09E.pdf

³⁸ *Request for information: Private remote sensing satellite disposal and debris mitigation*. (2024, March 8). Federal Register, 89 Fed. Reg. 13652. <https://www.federalregister.gov/documents/2024/03/08/2024-05004/request-for-information-private-remote-sensing-satellite-disposal-and-debris-mitigation>

³⁹ *Ibid*.

⁴⁰ Edwards, J. (2024, March 8). NOAA Office of Space Commerce's CRSRA Division seeks input on satellite disposal, debris mitigation regulations. ExecutiveGov, para 1. <https://executivegov.com/2024/03/noaa-office-of-space-commerces-crsra-division-seeks-input-on-satellite-disposal-debris-mitigation-regulations/>

⁴¹ *Supra* note 38.

⁴² *Supra* note 40, para 6.

⁴³ *Supra* note 36, para 3.

⁴⁴ *Ibid*, para 2.

In an effort to address the regulatory gaps and overlap between federal agencies' regulation of orbital debris, a legislative proposal was introduced to establish a licensing process for private sector novel space activities, aligning with U.S. obligations under the OST.⁴⁵

5.2 Overarching Regulatory Frameworks: Mission Authorization

The current regulatory framework for the commercial space industry is thus fragmented among the FCC, NOAA, and the FAA, with NASA and the DOD playing advisory roles. In order to mitigate current challenges and anticipate future ones, a more seamless and flexible regulatory framework should be implemented. Proposed solutions include creating a "one-stop-shop" (e.g. a connected government model) where users connect through a central gateway to access services that may ultimately be provided by different government agencies.⁴⁶ This single government interface model could be implemented in a number of ways, for example, by consolidating regulatory functions within a single entity, or separating them with a primary agency designated to coordinate among the various entities.⁴⁷ However, concrete legislative action is needed in order to fully reallocate jurisdictional and regulatory authority. A critical legislative initiative aimed towards addressing this issue is mission authorization. It is, in brief, a proposed licensing regime that includes an authorization and supervision framework for novel space activities (e.g. new and emerging technologies, commercial habitats, in-space manufacturing, and on-orbit refueling).⁴⁸ Some experts argue that the DOT should be in charge of mission authorization, since it already regulates launch and reentry, while others advocate for the Department of Commerce (DOC).⁴⁹

It is important to note that mission authorization, or more specifically, filling the regulatory gaps currently present in the U.S.'s commercial space regulatory environment, is a binding international obligation under Article VI of the OST.⁵⁰ In 2015, Congress directed the Office of Science and Technology Policy (OSTP), a division under NASA, to produce an assessment of the current and future commercial space activities and recommend a regulatory framework (for mission authorization) that would satisfy the U.S.'s OST obligations.⁵¹

Currently, four proposals for mission authorization frameworks have emerged from the White House's National Space Council, the House Science Committee, the National Space Council Users' Advisory Group, and the Senate Commerce Committee. The White House's policy guidance, titled the *United States Novel Space Activities Authorization and Supervision Framework*, was released in December 2023.⁵² The framework calls for interagency coordination and regulatory updates utilizing existing authorities to address mission authorization. More significantly, it splits the control for novel space activities between the DOC and DOT in order to take advantage of their regulatory expertise and competencies. The DOT would have

⁴⁵ *Ibid*, para. 1.

⁴⁶ Sorge, M. (2017, August). Commercial space activity and its impact on U.S. space debris regulatory structure (p. 5). The Aerospace Corporation. <https://aerospace.org/sites/default/files/2018-05/CommercialDebrisRegulation.pdf>

⁴⁷ *Ibid*.

⁴⁸ *Supra* note 44, para. 3.

⁴⁹ Smith, M. (2023, December 6). UAG endorses single agency for mission authorization. SpacePolicyOnline. <https://spacepolicyonline.com/news/uag-endorses-single-agency-for-mission-authorization/>

⁵⁰ Hitchens, T. (2023, November 29). White House plan for 'novel' space activities faces industry, Hill skepticism. Breaking Defense, para 5. <https://breakingdefense.com/2023/11/white-house-plan-for-novel-space-activities-faces-industry-hill-skepticism/>

⁵¹ Executive Office of the President, Office of Science and Technology Policy. (2016, April 4). *Report under Section 108 of the Commercial Space Launch Competitiveness Act*. https://obamawhitehouse.archives.gov/sites/default/files/microsites/ostp/csla_report_4-4-16_final.pdf

⁵² White House. (2023, December). *United States Novel Space Activities Authorization and Supervision Framework*. The White House. <https://www.whitehouse.gov/wp-content/uploads/2023/12/Novel-Space-Activities-Framework-2023.pdf>

authority over all human spaceflight activities, including missions to the moon, or other planets, as well as activities in Earth's orbit, and would license the transportation of materials in space and to the surface of the moon. The DOC would be granted more authority to regulate other uncrewed space activities (e.g. in-space servicing, assembly, and manufacturing, and active debris removal).

Critics of the White House's draft bill commented that its recommendations were out of step with both the House and Senate, and more importantly, the White House's draft bill split of control for novel space activities does nothing to streamline the regulation of the commercial space industry.⁵³ Additionally, as currently drafted, the current White House bill would allow government authorities such as the Department of Defense to put conditions on licenses to ensure national security, national interest, or space sustainability, causing challenges to arise regarding the interpretation of ambiguous language.⁵⁴

In contrast, representatives Frank Lucas (R-OK), House Science Committee Chairman, and Brian Babin (R-TX), Science Subcommittee on Space and Aeronautics chairman, introduced the Commercial Space Act of 2023.⁵⁵ The proposed Act seeks to establish a certification process for private spacecraft and space objects not currently licensed by U.S. agencies and would provide a statutory basis for regulating all commercial space activities, including debris mitigation. In stark contrast to the White House proposal, the Commercial Space Act would consolidate authority within the Department of Commerce, as opposed to splitting authorities between the DOT and NOAA. Additionally, the bill does not establish a traditional licensing regime; instead, it establishes a "passive process" that presumes approval unless the Department of Commerce denies an application within a 60-day timeframe.

Subsequently, in December 2023, the National Space Council's (NSC) User's Advisor group⁵⁶ released its own recommendations on a mission authorization framework to streamline the oversight of commercial space activities. Like the proposed Commercial Space Act, this framework aims to consolidate regulatory authority under a single agency, the DOC, addressing the fragmentation and overlap that currently characterize the U.S. orbital debris mitigation regime.

Lastly, the Senate Commerce Committee continues to work on developing its own commercial space bill. And, while the final draft has not been released, like its draft predecessors, the Senate's proposal will affirm the need for a mission authorization framework and is expected to consolidate mission authorization responsibilities within the Department of Commerce.

Thus, much of the holdup for mission authorization stems from a lack of consensus by policymakers. However, while much has been written about OST compliance, the U.S. has received no specific international criticism on the issue thus far. Moreover, the current, fragmented regulatory environment (existing as split jurisdiction between the FCC, FAA, and NOAA), still provides a robust mechanism of oversight for U.S. private sector space activities.⁵⁷ Furthermore, despite the lack of a concrete mission authorization framework, U.S. space companies have continued to produce technological innovation and increase the amount of capital flowing through the commercial space industry. In recent years, "Intuitive Machines made the first successful commercial lunar landing, Varda Space returned its orbital drug processing capsule, and SpaceX conducted multiple Starship test launches and its groundbreaking Polaris Dawn Mission, among other achievements from dozens of companies."⁵⁸ In considering these

⁵³ *Supra* note 50, para. 2-3.

⁵⁴ *Ibid.*

⁵⁵ *Supra* note 44, para. 8.

⁵⁶ The UAG is a federal advisory committee established to ensure that the views of the private sector and nongovernmental commercial space stakeholders are provided to the NSC.

⁵⁷ *Supra* note 44, para. 4.

⁵⁸ *Supra* note 44, para. 5.

accomplishments, another solution would be to focus on streamlining existing processes in order to keep pace with the industry before turning to mission authorization.

6. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE TRAJECTORY

Regardless, the fragmented regulatory environment in the United States is an issue that must be addressed in light of the increasing occupancy of outer space and the subsequent proliferation of debris. The U.S.'s current framework, which is spread across multiple agencies, including the FCC, FAA, and NOAA, has created inefficiencies and regulatory gaps that obstruct effective mitigation efforts. While each agency plays a vital role within its area of expertise, their overlapping jurisdictions and limited statutory scopes underscore the urgent need for a cohesive and streamlined regulatory approach.

The FCC has taken proactive steps to address orbital debris through updating its licensing requirements, but its unilateral rulemaking actions have sparked debates about statutory overreach and the need for greater interagency coordination. Similarly, the FAA's proposed rules on launch vehicle disposal and NOAA's evolving role in regulating remote sensing activities highlight the growing acknowledgement that orbital debris is a pressing concern that must be addressed. However, these efforts remain piecemeal, and without a unified mission authorization framework, the U.S. risks falling behind in fostering both a sustainable and competitive space industry.

To address these challenges, policymakers must prioritize regulatory clarity and interagency collaboration to create a seamless yet flexible framework for orbital debris mitigation. This regulatory clarity could even be something as limited as altering existing processes such that they are streamlined and as efficient as possible. Such a framework should also align with the best international practices, comply with international treaty obligations, incentivize innovation, and ensure the long-term sustainability of space activities. As the space economy continues to grow, the United States has a unique opportunity to lead by example in tackling orbital debris, safeguarding the future of space exploration, and maintaining its position as a global leader in the space industry.

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Exploring Strange New Legal Worlds: Navigating the Spectral Limits of Outer Space Treaty Interpretation in Light of the Moon Agreement

Kelsie C.M. Jackson¹

ABSTRACT

From valuable metals and nuclear power to scientific discovery, outer space presents profitability and power for those with the means to sail its seas. Human civilization demands the natural resource exploitation of Earth and often pursues the depletion of resources with little regard for future implications, rendering space resource exploitation an inevitable desideratum. Indeed, humanity faces the choice of allowing the pernicious and boorish consumption of space resources or of upholding international law to govern space exploitation in a peaceful manner.

Five United Nations treaties dictate the proper use of space. Articles I and II of the Outer Space Treaty serve as the paramount principle within space law by affording the freedom to use space to all humankind. However, the extent of exploitation an actor may conduct remains unclear because the treaty alludes to a quasi-paradox by requiring space activities to benefit all countries, banning appropriation of space, and guaranteeing the freedom to use — commercially exploit — space. The most recent space treaty, the Moon Agreement, attempts to resolve this paradox by sanctioning lunar exploitation under the implementation of an international regime. However, the treaty lacks support from major space-faring states, rendering space a legal quagmire. I delimit Articles I and II of the Outer Space Treaty to determine the legal obligations imposed on space actors using the unaccepted overinclusive language of the Moon Agreement, concluding the Outer Space Treaty independently necessitates a regime to govern space exploitation.

KEYWORDS: space resource exploitation, Outer Space Treaty, international legal regime, Moon Agreement, freedom of use

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1. INTRODUCTION: A NOVEL APPROACH

Outer space offers vast and untapped potential: scientific knowledge, strategic positions, and extractable resources lie scattered across its expanse. As commercial and governmental actors accelerate their extraterrestrial activities, international law struggles to define the legality of resource use. Human civilization demands natural resource exploitation and often pursues the depletion of resources with little regard for future implications, rendering space resource exploitation an inevitable desideratum.² A new space race dawns as commercial space actors rise. Competing interests and unchecked ambition inevitably lead to conflict. Indeed, humanity faces the choice of allowing the pernicious consumption of space resources or of upholding international law to govern space exploitation in a peaceful manner.³

The soul of the space law constellation, the 1967 Outer Space Treaty reserves space exclusively for peaceful purposes and governs basic legal issues that may arise during space activities.⁴ Yet, the Treaty ultimately remains one of principles—lacking the overt specificity and substance required to legally justify resource exploitation with ease.⁵ It only provides a serpentine justification—containing several cumbersome caveats—for the legality of resource exploitation within Articles I and II.⁶ Indeed, Articles I and II allude to a quasi-paradox by framing space as an inclusive environment that permits exploitation of space but not appropriation.⁷ This quasi-paradox stands at the heart of modern resource law debates.⁸ The subsequent 1979 Moon Agreement attempts to resolve this tension by reiterating Outer Space Treaty principles and explicitly sanctioning lunar exploitation with implementation of a governing international regime.⁹ However, the lack of state acquiescence to the Moon Agreement renders it extraneous in practice.¹⁰

² See generally Bilder, Richard B. (2009). A Legal Regime for the Mining of Helium-3 on the Moon: US Policy Options. *Fordham International Law Journal*, 69(2), 243-299, 251; David, L. (2019). *Moon Rush: The New Space Race*. (2019). National Geographic, 156-57. Indeed, Helium-3 represents one of the most commercially profitable prospects for exploitation on the moon. *Ibid.* See also Elvis, M. et al. (2021). Concentrated Lunar Resources: Imminent Implications for Governance and Justice. *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society A*, 379(2188), 1-21, 2 for a thorough and scientific description of potentially valuable resources present on the moon for commercial exploitation.

³ McDougal, M.S. (1963). Enjoyment and Acquisition of Resources in Outer Space. *University of Pennsylvania Law Review* 111(5), 521-636, 539. Because “relevant resources are . . . concentrated and dispersed in many different modalities and degrees,” conflict over right to access is likely. *Ibid.*

⁴ Treaty on Principles Governing the Activities of States in the Exploration and Use of Outer Space, including the Moon and Other Celestial Bodies, *opened for signature* Jan. 27, 1967, 18 U.S.T. 2410, 610 U.N.T.S. 205 (entered into force October 10, 1967) [hereinafter Outer Space Treaty].

⁵ Paxson, E.W. (1993). Sharing the Benefits of Outer Space Exploration: Space Law and Economic Development. *Michigan Journal of International Law*, 14(3), 487-517, 489. See also De Man, P. (2016). *Exclusive Use in an Inclusive Environment*. Springer, 79 (reasoning treaty writers left “property rights in natural resources” to “the background” in favor of resolving more pressing issues of sovereignty and peace).

⁶ Tronchetti, F. (2009). *Exploitation of Natural Resources of the Moon and Other Celestial Bodies: A Proposal for a Legal Regime*. Brill, 4 (noting the Treaty uses “general language” and omits language concerning “exploitation”).

⁷ *Ibid.* at 230.

⁸ *Ibid.*

⁹ See Agreement Governing the Activities of States on the Moon and Other Celestial Bodies, *opened for signature* Dec. 18, 1979, 1363 U.N.T.S. 22 (entered into force July 11, 1984) [hereinafter Moon Agreement]. See also Davis, M. E. & Lee, R. L. (1999). Twenty Years After the Moon Agreement and Its Legal Controversies. *Australian International Law Journal* 9-32, 10 (arguing the Moon Agreement “expands on the principles embraced in the Outer Space Treaty”).

¹⁰ See Paxson, *supra* note 5, at 497. Currently, parties to the Moon Agreement include Armenia, Australia, Austria, Belgium, Chile, Kazakhstan, Kuwait, Lebanon, Mexico, Morocco, Netherlands, Pakistan, Peru, Philippines, Turkey, Uruguay, and Venezuela. *Agreement Governing the Activities of States on the Moon and Other Celestial Bodies Participant*. The United Nations Office for Disarmament Affairs. September 29, 2014, from

Consequently, the politically frail Moon Agreement and general Outer Space Treaty stalemates analysis of legal obligations imposed on space exploiters.

To escape the stalemate, this Article introduces a novel approach—spectral treaty interpretation—which situates the Outer Space Treaty along a spectrum of subsequent legal instruments. With the Moon Agreement marking the outermost ceiling of acceptable readings of the Outer Space Treaty, spectral interpretation treats subsequent, more detailed instruments as directional beacons that confine earlier, principle-heavy language without displacing it. Spectral interpretation consists of a metaphorical approach to treaty interpretation by placing legal instruments upon a spectrum—see *Figure 1*—to realize a range of possible interpretations based on the relationships between the treaty. This approach conceives treaty interpretation as a fluctuation along a spectrum, recognizing the impact of successive treaties or other contextual developments rather than focusing on a single isolated and uncontextualized instrument. Article 31 of the Vienna Convention on the Law of Treaties provides doctrinal support for this method, instructing interpreters to read treaties considering their “context” so that *ut res magis valeat quam pereat*—legal instruments must operate, not fail.¹¹ While the Moon Agreement lacks binding authority, it still carries nuanced context for what discerning the legal obligations the Outer Space Treaty does—and does not—impose.

Spectral Treaty Interpretation

Figure 1

The idea that a later, more operational instrument calibrates rather than supplants the legal obligations of an earlier treaty already underpins two mature treaty regimes.¹² In the sea context, the 1994 Agreement

<https://treaties.unoda.org/t/moon/participants>. Saudi Arabia withdrew from the Agreement on January 5, 2024—further demonstrating the lack of enthusiasm regarding the attempt to regulate lunar resource exploitation. *Ibid.*

¹¹ United Nations Convention on the Law of Treaties, opened for signature May 23, 1969, 1155 U.N.T.S. 331 (entered into force January 27, 1980) [hereinafter Vienna Convention], Art. 31(1); Gardiner, R. (2015). *Treaty Interpretation* (2nd ed.). Oxford University Press, 179-180 (“requir[ing] a preference for an interpretation which gives a term some meaning rather than none”). Parties to the Outer Space Treaty and parties to the Moon Agreement are not identical, but that very fact provides insight into interpretation of the Outer Space Treaty. Kadelbach, S. (2018). The International Law Commission and Role of Subsequent Practice as a Means of Interpretation Under Articles 31 and 32 VCLT. *QIL Zoom In*, 46, 5-18, 8 (“Subsequent agreement must be ‘regarding the interpretation’ and the application of the treaty.”).

¹² See *ibid.* at Art. 31(3)(c) (requiring interpreters to consider “relevant rules of international law”); Agreement Relating to the Implementation of Part XI of the United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea of 10 December 1982, opened for signature, July 28, 1994, 1836 U.N.T.S. 3, Art. 2(1) [hereinafter Part XI Implementation Agreement]; Nagoya Protocol on Access to Genetic Resources and the Fair and Equitable Sharing of Benefits Arising from Their Utilization, opened for signature, Oct. 29, 2010, 3008 U.N.T.S. 3, Art. 4(1) [hereinafter Nagoya Protocol].

Relating to the Implementation of Part XI of United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea declares it “shall be interpreted and applied together with Part XI as a single instrument,” thereby fixing the upper limit of what the original seabed-mining articles may require.¹³ The Seabed Disputes Chamber’s 2011 advisory opinion has since treated the Agreement’s streamlined, market-oriented rules as the controlling gloss on States’ due diligence duties.¹⁴ A parallel dynamic operates in biodiversity law. Parties interpret the 1992 Convention on Biological Diversity’s open-ended promise of “fair and equitable benefit-sharing” through the procedure laid down by the 2010 Nagoya Protocol.¹⁵ The Protocol serves as a supplementary accord many States accept as the practical ceiling of their Article 15 commitments and that the EU has transposed verbatim into Regulation 511/2014.¹⁶ These analogues confirm that spectral interpretation is not an idiosyncratic innovation; it systematizes a well-established, Vienna-Convention-compliant method where later legal instruments operate as directional beacons that prevent earlier, principle-heavy treaties from being stretched beyond contemporary consensus.¹⁷ This is precisely the role the Moon Agreement can play vis-à-vis the Outer Space Treaty.

Anchoring the Outer Space Treaty’s open-textured freedoms to the Moon Agreement—however sparsely ratified—therefore reconciles commercial viability with inclusivity and supplies a principled, doctrinally orthodox pathway for regulators and courts to evaluate exploitative projects pending a comprehensive multilateral regime. If law is to govern the final frontier, its interpretive lenses must evolve as rapidly as the technologies they regulate; spectral interpretation aims to provide precisely such an adaptive lens. This Article proceeds in four parts. Section II dissects the semantic reach of Outer Space Treaty terms. Section III glosses three construals of Article I’s benefits clause and defends a positive yet flexible legal duty calibrated just short of the Moon Agreement’s equitable-sharing mandate. Sections IV and V reconceptualize Article II’s non-appropriation principle, distinguishing territorial areas from divisible resources to explain why *in-situ* resource use remains non-appropriative.

¹³ Part XI Implementation Agreement, *supra* note 12, at Art. 2(1) (“shall be interpreted and applied together with Part XI as a single instrument”).

¹⁴ *Responsibilities and Obligations of States Sponsoring Persons and Entities with Respect to Activities in the Area* (Advisory Opinion), Case No. 17, 2011 I.T.L.O.S. Rep. 10, ¶¶ 131-35 (Seabed Disputes Chamber) (applying the less onerous standards written into the 1994 Agreement’s Annex, Section 5—rather than the original, more rigid procedures of 1982 Part XI). Because ITLOS is a standing international tribunal whose opinions are widely cited, the decision supplies a persuasive comparative precedent: if courts interpret UNCLOS through its later implementing agreement, it is reasonable to interpret the Outer Space Treaty through the Moon Agreement to determine the maximum content of Articles I & II.

¹⁵ Convention on Biological Diversity Art. 15, June 5, 1992, 1760 U.N.T.S. 79 [hereinafter CBD]; Nagoya Protocol, *supra* note 12, at PmbL, Arts. 6-7. Because Articles 6 and 7 the Nagoya Protocol spell out how the benefit-sharing principle must be carried out in practice, they are the clearest illustration of an operational layer that gives teeth to CBD Article 15—mirroring the way the Moon Agreement, arguably, operates as a ceiling setting elaboration for Outer Space Treaty Articles I and II.

¹⁶ See Regulation 511/2014, of the European Parliament and of the Council of 16 Apr. 2014, Official Journal of the European Union, L 150/59 (transposing Nagoya’s procedures as the authoritative elaboration of CBD obligations despite non-universal ratification).

¹⁷ See generally Vienna Convention, *supra* note 11, at Art. 31(3)(c); Villiger, M. E. (2009). *Commentary on the 1969 Vienna Convention on the Law of Treaties*. Brill. 433-37 (discussing the role of subsequent agreements in interpretation).

2. THE SEMANTIC REACH OF ARTICLE I

Article I ensures three space freedoms—access, exploration, and use.¹⁸ These freedoms establish a legal framework enabling all states to carry out space activities without discrimination and provide legal justification for space exploitation. Article I additionally imposes a benefits provision by requiring “use of outer space . . . be carried out for the benefit and in the interest of all . . .”¹⁹ Undoubtedly, this language imposes a legal constraint—however vague—on a space actor’s ability to exercise exclusive control over space resources.²⁰ However, the exact scope of this legal obligation remains unclear. Spectral interpretation first asks: what is the maximum interpretation Article I can bear before it collapses into the Moon Agreement’s more exacting language? That ceiling cannot be exceeded; yet anything short of it remains potentially incompatible with the Outer Space Treaty.

2.1. Defining the Space Freedoms

The freedom to *use* space serves as the crux for *exploiting* space—commercially or otherwise. Doctrinally, *exploration* comprises an activity directed toward the improvement of knowledge but contains no “explicitly stated goal of immediate practical application.”²¹ *Use* pursues functional ends “beyond space itself,” thus *use* allows for “interests” to be “transformed into actionable goals.”²² In this context, *use* reasonably serves as a synonym of exploitation—in the context of space law.²³ Thus, exploitation of space involves the transformation of resources into value.²⁴ The Outer Space Treaty omits the term *exploitation*.

However, the Moon Agreement places the terms *use* and *exploitation* within the same conceptual framework as the Outer Space Treaty.²⁵ Article 11(5) dictates:

States Parties to this Agreement hereby undertake to establish an international regime, including appropriate procedures, to govern the exploitation of the natural resources of the Moon *as such exploitation is about to become feasible*.²⁶

Under a spectral lens, the term’s placement is decisive.²⁷ The Moon agreement presupposes that *exploitation* is a subset of *use* because the underlying right to use space already exists.²⁸ If exploitation were excluded

¹⁸ Outer Space Treaty, *supra* note 4, at Art. I. *See also e.g.* Larson, P.B. (2021). Is There a Legal Path to Commercial Mining on the Moon? *University of Pittsburgh Law Review*, 83(1), 1-50, 13-14 (discussing Article I’s guarantee of free lunar use); Hobe, S. and De Man, P. (2017). National Appropriation of Outer Space and State Jurisdiction to Regulate the Exploitation, Exploration and Utilization of Space Resources, *Zeitschrift für Luft-und Weltraumrecht German Journal of Air and Space Law* 66(3), 460-475, 474 (explaining the “equal interest” of all states in space”).

¹⁹ Outer Space Treaty, *supra* note 4, at Art. I.

²⁰ *See* Larson, *supra* note 18, at 12 (“The Moon is not free for unlimited commercial exploitation”); McDougal, *supra* note 3, at 543 (“The probabilities appear excellent that the general community will not regard many of the more important resources of space as subject to exclusive appropriation”).

²¹ De Man, *supra* note 5, at 79-80.

²² *Ibid.*, 80 (citing L. Peyrefitte. (1993). *Droit de l’espace*. Dalloz, 230; 232-33).

²³ Tronchetti, *supra* note 5, at 223.

²⁴ *Compare* Outer Space Treaty, *supra* note 4, at Art. I (omitting the term “exploitation”) with Moon Agreement, *supra* note 8, at Art. 11(5) (“international regime . . . to govern the exploitation of natural resources of the Moon.”)

²⁵ *Ibid.*

²⁶ Moon Agreement, *supra* note 8, at Art. 11(5) (emphasis added).

²⁷ *See* De Man, *supra* note 5, at 83-4 (arguing the lexical appearance of “exploitation” only in the Moon Agreement, not the Outer Space Treaty, is crucial for interpreting the latter through the former).

²⁸ *Ibid.* at 84-85.

form the Moon Agreement, Article 11(5) would outrun the Outer Space Treaty and consequently fail as the ceiling of the spectrum of possible interpretations.²⁹ Therefore, the Outer Space Treaty's term *use* must be wide enough to encompass commercial exploitation, subject to Article II and the benefits provision analyzed below.³⁰ Recent state practice confirms this functional reading. The United States and Luxembourg both premise private resource rights on the Outer Space Treaty's freedom of *use*.³¹ The Artemis Accords explicitly state in Section 10 that resource activities "shall be conducted under the auspices of, and consistent with, the Outer Space Treaty."³² None of these instruments attempts to amend Article I. They interpret *use* to include exploitation—exactly the move spectral interpretation predicts.³³

2.2. Defining Benefits

The term *benefit* remains undefined in Article I(1), but denotes something positive, useful, or profitable in ordinary parlance.³⁴ In practice, benefits may include scientific knowledge, raw materials, monetary profit, or technological advancements.³⁵ Nevertheless, what qualifies as a benefit may dramatically differ between states.³⁶ Raw lunar regolith may present immediate value to an industrialized state and little value to a state lacking the necessary processing infrastructure. This variability renders the benefits provision incredibly difficult to operationalize.

Despite the idiomatic nature of the term *benefits*, it untenable to read Article I(1) as allowing each state to dictate the exact benefits they receive.³⁷ Article I(1) by no means requires States to disgorge the entirety of their gains from a space activity.³⁸ Suggesting otherwise renders commercial exploitation endeavors into charitable enterprises. Certainly, forbidding exclusive rights to space benefits stanches development of infrastructure and slows humanity's enjoyment of resources.³⁹

Spectral interpretation buttresses this argument. The Moon Agreement supplies the interpretative ceiling by nearly repeating the Outer Space Treaty benefits provision verbatim⁴⁰ and further requiring the "equitable sharing" of "the benefits derived from" lunar "resources."⁴¹ The Outer Space Treaty, lacking the modifier, must impose a less prescriptive but still meaningful legal obligation. Accepted treaty

²⁹ *C.f.* Vienna Convention, *supra* note 11, at Art. 31(3)(c) (requiring interpretation in light of subsequent agreements) and De Man, *supra* note 4, at 84-5 (explaining subsequent instruments cannot expand obligations beyond the earlier treaty it elaborates). Nothing in the Moon Agreement purports to grant a right stand-alone of exploitation. Article 11(5) presumes that exploitation is already legal.

³⁰ De Man, *supra* note 5, at 84-85.

³¹ Commercial Space Launch Competitiveness Act, Public Law No. 114-90, § 51303, 129 Stat. 704, 720 (2015) (declaring U.S. nationals may obtain space resources "in accordance with applicable law, including the Outer Space Treaty"); Loi du 20 juillet 2017 relative à l'exploration et à l'utilisation des ressources de l'espace art. 2, 2017 Mém. A 674 (Lux.) (same premise).

³² Artemis Accords § 10 (Oct. 13, 2020) <https://www.nasa.gov/specials/artemis-accords/> (last visited Apr. 17, 2025).

³³ All instruments cite Outer Space Treaty Article I as their legal basis rather than proposing an amendment to the Treaty.

³⁴ Black's Law Dictionary. (2024). Benefit. In *Black's Law Dictionary* (12th ed). Thomson West.

³⁵ *Ibid.*

³⁶ Lee, R. J. (2012) *Law and Regulation of Commercial Mining of Minerals in Outer Space*. Springer, 156.

³⁷ *Ibid.* *E.g.*, Larson, *supra* note 17 at, 47 (describing the international recognition of remote sensing technology as a "universal benefit . . . even if the remote sensing occurred by commercial satellites").

³⁸ De Man, *supra* note 4, at 156.

³⁹ MacKay, M.A. (2020). Comment: Property Rights in Celestial Bodies: A Question of Pressing Concern. *Marquette Law Review*, 104(2), 575, 582.

⁴⁰ See De Man, *supra* note 4, at 44-5.

⁴¹ Moon Agreement, *supra* note 8, at Art. 11(7)(d).

interpretation methods affixes “the ordinary meaning” to words—meaning the term *benefits* should have a relatively similar meaning in both treaties regardless of the Moon Agreement’s requirement of equitable sharing.⁴² As such, Article I charges space actors with ensuring their activities yield benefits—tangible or intangible—available to all humankind while leaving each actor to choose an appropriate distribution mechanism.

3. BENEFITS PROVISION: AN ASPIRATION OR POSITIVE LEGAL OBLIGATION?

Building on the foundational analysis of Article I’s language, this section explores competing interpretations of the benefits provision and examines how commercial exploitation may—or may not—be deemed legal under the Outer Space Treaty. The restrictions on space activities enshrined by the Outer Space Treaty esteem space as an inclusive environment. Commercial activity—by its nature—tends to benefit a limited few. Article I(1) specifically requires all space actors carry out the use—or exploitation—and exploration of space for the benefit of all States.⁴³ This tension prompts a key question—does Article I(1) requirement permit commercial exploitation? The provision does not expressly prohibit commercial exploitation, but its meaning and legal force remain open to interpretation. Whether Article I(1) requires a diffuse and general benefit for all of humanity, tailored benefits gifted to each individual state, or something in between remains unclear.⁴⁴ The benefits provision fails to unequivocally ban commercial activity; however, the question remains as to whether any commercial activity successfully meets the requirements of Article I(1).⁴⁵

3.1. Potential Interpretations of the Benefits Provision

Facially, the benefits provision hinders commercial enterprise, especially if exclusivity is seen as incompatible with inclusivity.⁴⁶ At least three isolatable construals of Article I(1) exist that allow for commercial use of space.⁴⁷ Each construal reconciles exploitation with the benefits provision in different ways. These construals are also best understood along a spectrum of legal interpretation—displayed in

⁴² See Vienna Convention, *supra* note 10, at Art. 31(1).

⁴³ Outer Space Treaty, *supra* note 3, at Art. I(1). In full, the benefits requirement states that “exploration and use of outer space, including the Moon and other celestial bodies, shall be carried out for the benefit and in the interests of all countries, irrespective of their degree of economic or scientific development, and shall be the province of all mankind.” *Ibid.* Bohacek, P., et al. (2022). Benefit-Sharing as Investment Protection for Space Resource Utilization. *New Space*, 10(2), 127-135, 128 (reasoning that the Article I language indicates the existence of an obligatory sharing of benefits).

⁴⁴ Bohacek, et al., *supra* note 42, at 128. See also Lee, *supra* note 8, at 156. Recall, the Cold War encouraged treaty framers to write a treaty facilitating peace in space, not exploitation of space. Babcock, H.M. (2019). The Public Trust Doctrine, Outer Space, and the Global Commons: Time to Call Home ET. *Syracuse Law Review*, 69(2), 191-262, 206-07; Berkley, R. (1996). Space Law Versus Space Utilization: The Inhibition of Private Industry in Outer Space, *Wisconsin International Law Journal*, 15(2), 421-444, 421-22.

⁴⁵ De Man, *supra* note 4, at 184; Bohacek, et al., *supra* note 42, at 128 (“Article I of the OST . . . remains . . . the most unclear issue in the existing international space law regime”).

⁴⁶ Lee, *supra* note 8, at 160.

⁴⁷ *Ibid.* at 158. Lee uses the three construals to isolate the “possible outcomes and the corresponding applications on the exploration and extraction segments of a commercial space mining operation.” *Ibid.*

Figure 2—bounded by the Moon Agreement’s equity focused model at one extreme and a laissez-fair reading of the Outer Space Treaty at the other.

On the first construal, *the language holds an aspirational nature and imposes little to no legal obligation on sharing the benefits of space activities or exploitation of extracted resources.*⁴⁸ Should the language of Article I(1) only constitute a moral vision to guide space activities, it poses no obligation on exploiters to share the benefits of their space activities with non-space-faring States.⁴⁹ Thus, exploiters may share any

Figure 2

benefits voluntarily as they see fit. As well, conceiving of the benefits provision places little obligation on space actors to ensure the ability of others to conduct similar space activities. Perhaps, Article I(1) expresses a “future goal” that *eventually* imposes legal obligations.⁵⁰ Nevertheless, this construal of Article I(1) defines space as a generally unreserved domain in terms of legal obligation.⁵¹

On the second construal, *the language imposes a legal obligation on sharing the benefits of space activities but not on sharing the benefits from the exploitation of extracted resources.*⁵² Under this construal, Article I(1) only imposes an obligation on an exploiter to ensure exploitative activities do not preclude another’s ability to conduct similar activities.⁵³ Thus, this construal relies on a dichotomy between the act of exploiting the Moon and the later use of the benefits accrued from the act of exploitation.⁵⁴

On the third construal, *the language imposes a legal obligation on both sharing the benefits of space activities and the exploitation of extracted resources.*⁵⁵ Article I(1) imposing a positive legal obligation on

⁴⁸ Lee, *supra* note 8, at 158 (explaining the benefits provision as a “generalised mission statement rather than [a] positive and specific duty.”). *See also* Bohacek, et al., *supra* note 42, at 129 (describing the Building Blocks for the Development of an International Framework on Space Resource Activities “call for an actor to give ‘due regard’ to the interest of all countries and humankind, not calling for any mandatory or concrete fulfilment of the OST Article I”).

⁴⁹ Nevertheless, commercial exploitation provides a “positive development for all States.” Lee, *supra* note 8, at 158.

⁵⁰ Paxson, *supra* note 4, at 492.

⁵¹ Lee, *supra* note 8, at 158.

⁵² *Ibid.* Lee defines this as “no more than a negative duty of ensuring that the activity does not cause a detriment to any State.” *Ibid.*

⁵³ *Ibid.*

⁵⁴ Lee, *supra* note 8, at 158.

⁵⁵ *Ibid.* Contrasting from the previous construal, Lee describes this as a “positive duty to share the benefits from space activities.” *Ibid.*

both space activities and the sharing of space benefits precludes the exploiter from retaining the right to *all* benefits reaped from an exploited resource.⁵⁶ As the second construal relies on a dichotomy between the act of exploiting the Moon and the later use of the benefits accrued from the act of exploitation, this construal relies on the notion that the use of the reaped benefits still entails use of space.⁵⁷

3.2. *Exploitation for the Benefit and in the Interest of All?*

Among these interpretations, the third construal best aligns with the structure and intent of the Treaty. The construal conceives of the act of removing the resource and the act of deriving commercial benefit remain indelibly tied as uses of space.

First, the benefits provision appears in the operative body of the Treaty—not the preamble—granting it legal effect.⁵⁸ The first construal erroneously frames Article I(1) as a moral vision—one inappropriate for a treaty article.⁵⁹ Even though Article I(1) lacks a mechanism of self-execution because the Treaty fails to delineate the appropriate means to conduct space activities in a way that benefits all States, it carries the weight of a “duly formulated contractual norm.”⁶⁰ Thus, Article I(1) imparts a positive legal obligation despite the lack of an enforcement mechanism.⁶¹ In fact, the Moon Agreement serves as an attempt to provide a mechanism—albeit a weak one—to Article I(1).⁶² Despite its unacceptance as a method to enact the benefits requirement, the attempt to implement a method to fulfill the requirement suggests Article I(1) requires practical application.⁶³ Therefore, Article I(1) imposes a positive legal obligation beyond the simple moral vision.

Second, construal two demands a “dichotomy” between the *use of space* and the *use of space resources*.⁶⁴ The dichotomy insisted by construal two relies on the act of exploiting a space resource for economic gain occurs on Earth and not in space.⁶⁵ This dichotomy creates a host of issues in practice. To illustrate, advanced lunar mining endeavors feasibly require lunar bases powered by mined lunar materials, but this use of the mined materials constitutes an act of exploitation not occurring on Earth. Therefore, in this scenario, the dichotomy insisted upon by construal two fails because the act of reaping value from the resource remains entangled with conduct in space. The dichotomy requires tedious and senseless analysis to determine the difference between the *use of space* and the *use of space resources* for each space activity.⁶⁶ Thus, treating post-extraction use as beyond the scope of the Outer Space Treaty artificially narrows the reach of the benefits provision.

⁵⁶ Ibid; Vakaki, A. (2022). A New Gold Mining Rush?. *Journal of Space Law*, 46(2), 421-463, 452 (“[M]ining of space resources would be legal as long as it is for the benefit of all humankind, therefore it would not be in accordance with international space law if such mining is carried out only for exclusive interests.”). Although this interpretation strictly adheres to the text of the Outer Space Treaty, Vakaki recognizes the United States as forging an opposing legal interpretation that allows nationals to privately benefit from their space exploits. Ibid.

⁵⁷ De Man, *supra* note 4, at 181.

⁵⁸ Paxson, *supra* note 4, at 492.

⁵⁹ Ibid.

⁶⁰ Ibid; Bohacek, et al., *supra* note 42, at 128 (“considering Article I as purely inspirational whereas other articles of the OST are to be legally binding has been criticized by man legal scholars”).

⁶¹ Tronchetti, *supra* note 5, at 24-25.

⁶² Lee, *supra* note 8, at 157.

⁶³ Ibid. at 158.

⁶⁴ De Man, *supra* note 4m at 157. Note, De Man applies this dichotomy to Art. II rather than Art. I. Nevertheless, the dichotomy provides salient analysis to Art. I as well.

⁶⁵ Ibid. at 157-58.

⁶⁶ De Man, *supra* note 4, at 171.

Third, Article I(1) specifically identifies the plural *interests*, harkening “specific and identifiable interests” rather than a vague and all-encompassing singular *interest* solely applicable to humankind.⁶⁷ The singular *interest* implies a collective good where States possess a moral obligation to better humanity through space exploitation.⁶⁸ In opposition, the plural *interests* implies space actors must conduct their activities in a way that appeals to the individual interests or needs of each country.⁶⁹ Moreover, the plural *interests* reflect the reality that different countries carry different interests; thus, the Outer Space Treaty principles necessitate a tailored benefit sharing scheme that considers the interests of the benefits receiver.⁷⁰

3.3. *The Moon Agreement’s Perspective on Benefit Sharing*

Because the Moon Agreement “may arguably constitute the further elaborations . . . to give effect to the” benefits provision, spectral interpretation constitutes a sound means to demarcate the possible legal meanings of the benefits provision.⁷¹ Under the spectral interpretation theory, the Outer Space Treaty must impose a less restrictive benefit sharing obligation than the one identified in the Moon Agreement. Yet, this observation provides little clarity. The Moon Agreement implements the same benefits provision stated in Outer Space Treaty Article I(1) but further elaborates by requiring consideration of “present and future generations as well as the need to promote higher standards of living and conditions of economic and social progress.”⁷² Presumably, the Agreement’s Article 11(5) international regime bears the responsibility of determining the extent of the “equitable” benefit sharing requirements.⁷³ The Agreement further declares the moon and its resources “the common heritage of mankind,” a concept absent from the Outer Space Treaty.⁷⁴ Such language indicates a requirement of inclusive use through the sharing of the benefits reaped from those resources, and the Agreement leaves it up to “the international community,” not “individual States and their nationals” to define the scope of the benefit sharing legal obligation.⁷⁵ The exclusion of the common heritage concept from the Outer Space Treaty indicates that while the Treaty may also contain a benefit sharing requirement, individual states may possess the right to unilaterally determine the scope of that requirement as applied to their nationals.⁷⁶

The Outer Space Treaty lacks any stated requirement of equitable distribution, and the very rejection of the Moon Agreement emphasizes the Outer Space Treaty’s lack of an equitable sharing requirement reflective of the common heritage of mankind concept. Clearly, the Outer Space Treaty must lack the strong legal obligations to benefit sharing presented in the Moon Agreement. An undeniable distribution obligation still emerges under both treaties when a space venture produces a benefit worth sharing. Even so, a space mining venture accords with the Outer Space Treaty by sharing *something* with all other states that benefits all.⁷⁷ Nevertheless, the question remains as to *how much* and *what* must be shared for mining ventures to remain

⁶⁷ Lee, *supra* note 8, at 157 (citing Cheng, B. (1998). *Studies in International Space Law*. Oxford University Press, 234-35).

⁶⁸ *Ibid.*

⁶⁹ *Ibid.*

⁷⁰ *Ibid.*; Bohacek, et al. *supra* note 42, at 132 (“each nation has different needs and interests, which eliminates the possibility of customizing the contribution to every single of them”).

⁷¹ Lee, *supra* note 8, at 157.

⁷² The Moon Agreement, *supra* note 8, at Art. 4.

⁷³ *Ibid.* at Art. 11(7).

⁷⁴ *Ibid.* at Art. 11(3).

⁷⁵ Goehring, J. (2021). Why Isn’t Outer Space a Global Commons? *National Security Law & Policy*, 11(573) 573-590, 579-80 (citing Cheng, B. (1998). *Studies in International Space Law*. Oxford University Press, 386).

⁷⁶ *Ibid.*

⁷⁷ Paxson, *supra* note 4, at 491 (“Article I imposes on nations binding obligations to share, even if these obligations remain ill-defined.”).

harmonious with Article I(1).⁷⁸ Despite these uncertainties, construal three provides a less stringent obligation compared to the Moon Agreement. By imposing a legal obligation on both sharing the benefits of space activities and the exploitation of extracted resources, construal three neither requires the Moon Agreement's governing regime nor the common heritage of mankind declaration. Having fixed the upper limit of benefit-sharing at the Moon Agreement's equitable-sharing clause, the analysis now turns to Article II's non-appropriation rule. The same spectrum applies: the Moon Agreement again provides the outermost ceiling, while a purely territorial reading forms the floor.

4. EXAMINING ARTICLE II OF THE OUTER SPACE TREATY

Spectral interpretation affirms that Article I of the Outer Space Treaty accommodates exploitation, yet a second hurdle remains in determining the legal obligations of space exploiters—the non-appropriation principle enshrined in Article II. Spectral interpretation treats an absence of regulation as the floor and the Moon Agreement's Article 11 as the ceiling. This Section locates lawful resource activities between these two poles. Our task is to locate lawful resource activities between these two poles. Where Article II remains silent, the Moon Agreement ceiling clarifies what remains prohibited and, by implication, permissible.

Read against the Moon Agreement, Article II restricts sovereignty and property claims—not resource extraction *per se*. Article II declares that “outer space, including the Moon and other celestial bodies, is not subject to national appropriation by claim of sovereignty, by means of use or occupation, or by any other means.”⁷⁹ Planting the U.S. flag on the lunar surface therefore conveyed no title to the land. The principle preserves the inclusive ethos that undergirds Article I's freedoms of access, exploration, and use. Determining the scope and effect of Article II requires the resolution of three main issues through spectral interpretation.⁸⁰ First, Article II expressly prohibits “national appropriation,” leaving the ability of non-national actors to appropriate unclear. Second, the phrase “by any other means” furnishes several competing interpretations of the definition of appropriation. Third, whether Article II applies to natural resources remains unclear. The Moon Agreement essential context and nuance for each inquiry.

4.1 To Whom Does the Ban Apply?

Although Article II speaks only of “national” appropriation, two treaty mechanisms extend the ban to private actors. First, interpreting Article II to private appropriation vacates the efficacy of the Outer Space Treaty as an insurer of space freedoms.⁸¹ Allowing private entity appropriation creates a legal loophole for states to appropriate space indirectly by owning a controlling share of a corporation, thereby eviscerating Article I's freedoms.⁸² Second, Article VI attributes “national activities . . . whether carried on by governmental or non-governmental entities” to the launching State and obliges it to authorize and continually supervise such activities.⁸³ Therefore, in public international law terms, the Outer Space Treaty

⁷⁸ Outer Space Treaty, *supra* note 3, at Art. I(1).

⁷⁹ Outer Space Treaty, *supra* note 3, at Art. II.

⁸⁰ See De Man, P. (2015-2016). The Exploitation of Asteroids and the Non-Appropriation Principle: Reflections on the Nature of Property Rights in Light of US Space Resources Act of 2015, 40(1-2), 1-55, 28 (discussing the controversy surrounding the legal scope of Article II).

⁸¹ Outer Space Treaty, *supra* note 4, at Art. I. Allowing an actor to claim ownership of an area in space inherently excludes another actor from using that area, violating the Outer Space Treaty's right to use and access all areas of space. *Ibid.*

⁸² *Ibid.*

⁸³ *Ibid.* at Art. VI.

converts private conduct into State responsibility.⁸⁴ Because State authorization is indispensable to sustain private property claims in space, any putative private appropriation necessarily violates the State's own obligations under Articles II and VI.⁸⁵ Therefore, if the state cannot appropriate the Moon, neither may its nationals because national approval—or lack of disapproval—of appropriative activities violates a state's obligations under Article IV.⁸⁶

4.2. *What Types of Appropriation does Article II Concern?*

The second problem concerns the types of appropriation included in Article II. Article II bans appropriation by claims of sovereignty, use, or occupation but omits enumeration of other methods to obtain exclusivity.⁸⁷ A strict reading might leave room for private real estate. The Moon Agreement clarifies the ceiling. Article 11(2) re-states the non-appropriation principle seen in the Outer Space Treaty, then in Article 11(3) iterates that “no State, international intergovernmental or non-governmental organization, national organization or non-governmental entity or . . . natural person” may claim the lunar surface or the “natural resources in place” as property.⁸⁸ If the Outer Space Treaty already forbade such property claims in Article II, then Article 11(3) would be “redundant.”⁸⁹ The presence of both articles signals that property qualifies as a subset of appropriation but does not necessarily qualify as co-extensive with appropriation.⁹⁰ Article II itself targets sovereignty claims and leaves property claims in a grey zone; under spectral interpretation, the Moon Agreement fixes the ceiling by outlawing property *in situ*, while allowing States latitude to regulate ownership of resources once removed from their natural context, provided Article I's benefit and Article II's non-sovereignty rules are respected.

4.3. *What is the Physical Scope of Article II?*

Neither the Outer Space Treaty nor the Moon Agreement defines the term *outer space*—leaving the physical scope of the non-appropriation principle ambiguous. Two interpretations exist: *sensu stricto* (the void between celestial bodies) and *sensu lato* (the void and matter contained therein).⁹¹ Article II states, “outer space, including the Moon and other celestial bodies, is not subject to national appropriation.”⁹² Both the Outer Space Treaty and the Moon Agreement fail to delineate what outer space constitutes, creating uncertainty.⁹³ Thus, should Article II only pertain to outer space *sensu stricto*, the ability to appropriate matter contained within outer space such as resources, relies on the definition of a celestial body because Article II specifies that outer space and celestial bodies are not subject to national appropriation.⁹⁴

Does the term *celestial body* capture all aggregate forms of matter in outer space, or does a celestial body have certain characteristics relevant to only certain arrangements of matter? Limiting a *celestial body* to a distinct class of objects renders the corporeal objects escaping this class appropriable—with the

⁸⁴ Cassese, Antonio. (2005). *International Law*. 2nd ed. Oxford University Press, 250; Tronchetti, *supra* note 5, at 30-31.

⁸⁵ Pop, V. (2009). *Who Owns the Moon? Extraterrestrial Aspects of Land and Mineral Resources*. Springer, 12.

⁸⁶ See Tronchetti, *supra* note 5, at 30.

⁸⁷ Lee, *supra* note 8, at 167

⁸⁸ Moon Agreement, *supra* note 8, at Art. 11(3).

⁸⁹ Lee, *supra* note 8, at 168.

⁹⁰ *Ibid.*

⁹¹ De Man, *supra* note 4, at 99-133.

⁹² Outer Space Treaty, *supra* note 3, at Art. II.

⁹³ Epstein, D. (2024). Protecting the Cosmos: Defining Celestial Bodies in the Outer Space Treaty. *Space and Defense*, 15(1), 35-56, 36.

⁹⁴ *Ibid.*

understanding that these objects “are too insignificant to constitute celestial bodies, yet at the same time cannot be assimilated with outer space *sensu stricto* because of their material manifestation.”⁹⁵ Under this logic, delimitation of a celestial body occurs based on the ability of humans to remove the object from its natural location.⁹⁶ Consequently, movable objects serve as non-celestial bodies while immovable objects serve as celestial bodies.⁹⁷ Article II must pertain to outer space *sensu stricto*, not *sensu lato*.⁹⁸ Second, a third category of objects necessarily exists beyond outer space *sensu stricto* and celestial bodies.⁹⁹ The physical characteristics of these objects apparently exclude them from the class of celestial bodies which allows these objects to elude application of Article II.¹⁰⁰

The wording of Article II marks a textual shift from the UN General Assembly Resolution 1962’s conjunctive “outer space *and* celestial bodies,” signaling that Article II embraces space *sensu lato*, rendering smaller forms of aggregate matter.¹⁰¹ Any interpretation of *celestial bodies* and *outer space* demands applicability to the remaining provisions of the Outer Space Treaty.¹⁰² Excluding non-celestial body matter from application of Article II allows a significant portion of outer space to remain unregulated by space law, and the freedom to use and explore these non-celestial body (and non-outer space *sensu stricto* objects) would not be guaranteed by Article I.¹⁰³

No acceptable criteria exists to delimit the nondescript class of objects from celestial bodies or outer space.¹⁰⁴ Neither the Moon Agreement nor the Outer Space Treaty include a specific definition of the physical phenomena it purports to cover.¹⁰⁵ Regardless of any rendering of the term *celestial body*, the non-appropriation principle must indiscriminately applies to both outer space and the matter within space given Article II pertains to outer space *sensu lato*.¹⁰⁶ Thus, an inclusive approach avoids the ontological hair-splitting of trying to precisely define *celestial bodies*.¹⁰⁷ Any attempt to exclude certain collections of matter from the celestial body category results in an ambiguous legal regime.

4.4. The Moon Agreement and Non-Appropriation

The Moon Agreement better articulates the scope of its non-appropriation principle compared to the Outer Space Treaty by emphasizing the inability of any person or entity to claim sovereignty and the non-appropriable nature of lunar natural resources in place. Reading the Moon Agreement stipulation in Article 11(3) that no actor may claim the “natural resources in place” as property in conjunction with the Article 11(2) restatement of the Outer Space Treaty’s non-appropriation principle demonstrates that the Outer Space Treaty imposes no ban on the appropriation of natural resources in place.¹⁰⁸ Otherwise, no need exists

⁹⁵ Ibid at 132.

⁹⁶ Lee, *supra* note 8, at 189.

⁹⁷ Ibid.

⁹⁸ De Man, *supra* note 4, at 133.

⁹⁹ Ibid.

¹⁰⁰ Ibid.

¹⁰¹ Ibid.; United Nations General Assembly. (1963). Declaration of Legal Principles Governing the Activities of States in the Exploration and Use of Outer Space (Resolution 1962 (XVIII)) (emphasis added). De Man, *supra* note 4, at 133.

¹⁰² Ibid. at 134.

¹⁰³ Ibid.

¹⁰⁴ Ibid.

¹⁰⁵ Ibid. at 135.

¹⁰⁶ Ibid.

¹⁰⁷ Ibid.

¹⁰⁸ See Moon Agreement, *supra* note 8, at Art. 11(5)-(3).

for Article 11(3) because the restated language of the Outer Space Treaty would already capture a ban on the appropriation of natural resources in place. Accordingly, Article II occupies the lower band of the spectrum while the Moon Agreement’s non-appropriation clauses anchor the ceiling; every lawful resource project must thread that interval—eschewing sovereignty or in-situ property.

5. DEFINING NATURAL RESOURCES IN TERMS OF ARTICLE II

The previous section deems a deductive delimitation of outer space and celestial bodies to determine whether any legal basis exists for invidious application of Article II untenable considering the determination Article II refers to outer space *sensu lato*. Attempts to draw hard lines between space, celestial bodies, and natural resources proves doctrinally difficult. Article II’s inclusive phrasing appears hostile to exploitation because most extraction entails at least a minutia of *de facto* exclusivity.¹⁰⁹ To reconcile the tension, this Section proceeds with refining what counts as a resource without resurrecting the physical characteristics tests already rejected in Section 4.

The space law treaties make scant references to natural resources. In fact, the Outer Space Treaty makes no reference to natural resources. However, the Moon Agreement references natural resources by declaring “natural resources in place” not subject to ownership and by deeming the resources of the Moon “the common heritage of mankind” in Article 11(3) and Article 11(5).¹¹⁰ The *in-place* qualifier implies that removed materials exit the non-appropriation zone and become subject to the freedom to use and the benefits provision.¹¹¹ Likewise, the International Telecommunication Constitution labels radio frequencies associated with Earth orbit as “limited natural resources,” confirming that space resources may be both tangible or intangible.¹¹² The following paragraphs discuss potential interpretations orienting the non-appropriation principle to the legality of exploitation. *Figure 3* depicts these models.

Figure 3

¹⁰⁹ Epstein, *supra* note 92, at 40.

¹¹⁰ Moon Agreement, *supra* note 8, at Art. 11(3); Art. 11(5).

¹¹¹ De Man, *supra* note 4 at, 172. Further, Article 1(3) of the Moon Agreement states the agreement does not concern “extraterrestrial materials which reach the surface of the Earth by natural means.” Moon Agreement, *supra* note 8, at Art. 1(3).

¹¹² The ITU Constitution is almost universally ratified and adhered to. International Telecommunication Union. (1992). Constitution of the International Telecommunication Union, Art. 44(2)

5.1. Interpretation One: Article II Bans Appropriation of All Resources

Article II institutes an all-encompassing ban on the appropriation of any space resource—both tangible and intangible—because the language of the Outer Space Treaty makes no clear-cut distinction between outer space including celestial bodies and the natural resources therein.¹¹³ Therefore, Article II necessarily bans any exploitative acts entailing appropriation.¹¹⁴ Nevertheless, this interpretation contradicts the freedom to use space, enshrined in Article I, because it limits space actors from committing certain exploitative acts. Furthermore, this interpretation seems contrary to Article I(1) declaration that the use of space exists as the “province of mankind.”¹¹⁵

5.2. Interpretation Two: Article II Bans Appropriation of Movable Resources

Article II bans the appropriation of immovable resources by human intervention. Thus, movable resources may be legally appropriated because either they no longer serve as a part of “the constituent body” or the entire collection of matter may be captured and moved from its natural location.¹¹⁶ Consequently, these movable items cannot be considered celestial bodies or part of outer space *sensu stricto*. Thus, this interpretation falls prey to the same conundrum as the attempt to define celestial bodies based on their physical characteristics—an entire class of objects escapes the purview of space law. Furthermore, hinging the application of Article II on the ability to move matter renders Article II an empty shell because as technology develops, the ability to move more substantial collections of matter increases.¹¹⁷ Additionally, distinguishing between movables and immovables leaves several questions unanswered. For example, given the immovable nature of an orbital slot, the occupation of said slot by a satellite serves as appropriation.

5.3. Interpretation Three: Article II Bans Appropriation of Indivisible Resources

Like the movable versus immovable approach, but perhaps more tenable, framing resource exploitation through a dichotomy between the area and resource reframes the application of Article II.¹¹⁸ This dichotomy differs from the approach discussed in Interpretation Three by preventing the appropriation of entire bodies of matter, such as asteroids.¹¹⁹ This interpretation understands Article II as a ban on the appropriation of resources which represents an indivisible part of the territory to which the resource originates.¹²⁰ Thus, Article II serves as a prohibition of sovereignty over territorial areas. Indeed, exploitation of a natural resource fails to entail a claim of appropriation because the natural resource only serves as a component of the territorial body, and the integrity of the body does not rely on its components.¹²¹ For example, the area/resource dichotomy allows for the use of geostationary orbit because while a satellite occupies an orbital slot, the existence of the satellite entails no claim of sovereignty over

¹¹³ *Ibid.* at 151.

¹¹⁴ *Ibid.*; Outer Space Treaty, *supra* note 3, at Art. II.

¹¹⁵ Lee, *supra* note 8, at 190.

¹¹⁶ De Man, *supra* note 4, at 153.

¹¹⁷ De Man, *supra* note 4, at 153 (citing Pritzsche, K.U. (1991). “Die Nutzung natürlicher Ressourcen” in Pritzsche, K.U. (E.d.) (1991). *Handbuch des Weltraumrechts*. Carl Heymanns, 567-68).

¹¹⁸ De Man, *supra* note 4, at 153.

¹¹⁹ *Ibid.* at 153; 157. See e.g., J. R. Brophy, et al. (2012). *Asteroid Retrieval Feasibility* [paper presentation]. 2012 IEEE Aerospace Conference, Big Sky, MT, United States (describing the scientific feasibility of forcing asteroid movement).

¹²⁰ De Man, *supra* note 4, at 153.

¹²¹ *Ibid.* at 179-206.

said area of space. However, the dichotomy between areas and resources presents an interpretation of Article II that does not rely on categorizing resources based on characteristics.

5.4. Exploitation based on Functionality

Interpretation three locates the lawful zone of exclusivity between Article II’s territorial floor and the Moon Agreement’s *in-situ* ceiling. To make that zone workable, this subsection adopts Philip De Man’s “exploitation exponent” concept and calibrates it to the spectral framework.¹²² An exploitation exponent is any slice of outer space reality—material or immaterial—whose economic or scientific value can be realized only through a transformation that, for a limited time, demands exclusive control.¹²³ Exclusivity therefore stands as derivative, not constitutive—it inheres in the function the actor performs, not the territory from which the actor draws the exponent (or resource).¹²⁴

Article I already classifies exploitation as a lawful form of use; the resources territory of origin and the resource itself are merely “two overlapping states of the same physical matter” distinguishable solely on functional terms.¹²⁵ That freedom of use, however, does not lift the activity out of Article II’s ambit—it simply means Article II cannot prohibit exclusive control, unless that control morphs into a sovereignty, property, or *de facto* claim.¹²⁶ A resource qualifies as an exploitation exponent the moment human intervention begins the transformation process—this could include digging, processing, and spectrum assignment. Vulnerability to exploitation, rather than physical traits like size or mobility defines a natural resource in space for legal purposes.¹²⁷ This encompasses both tangible and intangible assets and allows avoids fruitless debates about the status of a resource as a component of a celestial body or matter in outer space.¹²⁸

Because an exponent is defined by its transformation-linked value, the legality of excluding others hinges on whether exclusivity is *objectively necessary* to perform that transformation. Once the value is realized—or can be realized without exclusivity—the temporary right dissolves, preventing drift into permanent appropriation. Three treaty-based arguments establish such a distinction. First, characterizing exploitation in terms of both *use* and *appropriation* renders the Treaty self-defeating—an outcome the Vienna Convention repudiates.¹²⁹ Second, the Moon Agreement regulates exploitation in Article 11(5) and prohibits appropriation in Article 11(2), evidencing non-identity.¹³⁰ Third, the Outer Space Treaty contemplates exclusive control of lunar stations by permitting their existence.¹³¹ Exclusive use is thus not appropriation *per se*. The exploitation exponent doctrine operationalizes interpretation three without violating the Moon Agreement ceiling. It allows temporary, function bound exclusivity over severed resources while preserving Article II’s absolute ban on sovereignty and property *in situ*.¹³² Exclusive rights

¹²² Ibid. See also McDougal, *supra* note 2, at 547.

¹²³ De man *supra* note 4, at 180-81

¹²⁴ Ibid.

¹²⁵ Ibid. at 181.

¹²⁶ Ibid. at 180 (arguing that the freedom of use permits temporary, function-bound exclusivity over resources, but such exclusivity must cease once it would amount to a sovereignty or property claim). See also Tronchetti, *supra* note 6, at 220-224 (distinguishing lawful exploitation from unlawful exploitation under Articles I and II).

¹²⁷ De Man, *supra* note 4, at 183.

¹²⁸ Ibid. See also De Man, P. (2011). The Commercial Exploitation of Outer Space and Celestial Bodies: A Functional Solution to the Natural Resource Challenge. *IAC-10-E71.4*, 28-38, 33 (defining intangible space resources).

¹²⁹ Ibid.

¹³⁰ Moon Agreement, *supra* note 8, at Art. 11

¹³¹ Outer Space Treaty, *supra* note 3, at Art. XII

¹³² De Man, *supra* note 4, at 184.

expire at their end of functional necessity—consistent with the inclusive ethos that threads Articles I and II together.

6. CONCLUSION: SPECTRAL INTERPRETATION

The Outer Space Treaty furnishes a thorny legal quandary. It grants all states the right to exploit space while simultaneously forbidding appropriation. Read in a vacuum, Articles I and II appear to conflict. Using a spectrum anchored by the subsequent Moon Agreement, however, resolves that tension into a coherent legal doctrine. Spectral interpretation treats the Moon Agreement as the outer ceiling of acceptable readings and the principles of the Outer Space Treaty as the floor. Between those anchors, a practicable middle band emerges. First, Article I imposes a positive but flexible obligation. Actors must ensure that the advantages of their space activities remain accessible to all humankind. Second, Article II bans sovereignty or lasting property in territory and in-situ resources, yet allows temporary, function-bound exclusivity over exploitation exponents. Third, because Article VI attributes private conduct to States, every extraction project ultimately remains a matter of public accountability, closing the loophole of corporate sovereignty by proxy.

Under this reading, the Outer Space Treaty permits space exploitation as long as actors avoid making territorial claims, prevent exclusive domains, and share resulting benefits in some form. The scheme preserves the Outer Space Treaty's inclusive ethos while offering industry a clear legal pathway. States can embed the exploitation exponent doctrine and the positive legal obligation from the benefits provision into licensing frameworks, and international bodies can issue non-binding guidelines to harmonize practice. Spectral interpretation reframes the Treaties—not as a paradox to be solved by future diplomacy, but as a mechanism capable of guiding responsible resource development. As humanity's presence in space expands, spectral interpretation will remain indispensable by ensuring the Outer Space Treaty ethos boldly governs the final frontier, even alongside the reality of commercial ambition.

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The Limits Of National Sovereignty: An Analysis Of The Line Between Airspace And Space. Expanding On Space Law And Government (1963) By Andrew G. Haley

Kaya Robello,¹ Robert Krasanek² and Jonathan Kaley-Isley³

ABSTRACT

Andrew G Haley (19 November 1904 – 11 September 1966) was a renowned American lawyer who was instrumental in the development of modern space law. He and Dr. Theodore von Kármán together formed the Aerojet Engineering Corporation in 1942. Haley's seminal book "Space Law and Government" (1963) was written in the years after Sputnik, at the height of the Cold War, and several years prior to the signing of the Outer Space Treaty. In Chapter Four of his book, Haley recounts the essential arguments for establishing a scientific boundary, governed by the laws of physics and what he saw as the limits of current technology, between airspace and outer space. Haley argues that state sovereignty extends only to the point at which state interest exists, and that wherever space begins, it should not be subject to national jurisdiction. As part of the historical Haley Project, SCF Interns have updated and annotated chapters of his book. In this paper, we examine the arguments Haley made regarding how the law should demarcate between air and space. We note that Haley gives conflicting information regarding the calculation of the von Kármán line and what it is supposed to represent. Despite these ambiguities and subsequent critiques, the von Kármán line, largely through Haley's efforts, has become the prevailing, albeit pseudo-scientific, standard for defining the commencement of outer space in international law and practice.

KEYWORDS: national sovereignty, Karman line, global commons

1. INTRODUCTION

The term “national sovereignty” refers to a State’s independent authority to govern its domestic jurisdiction in accordance with international law. The *1944 Convention on International Civil Aviation* established that a State has complete and exclusive sovereignty over the airspace above its territory. By

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the time of his 1963 book “Space Law and Government”, Andrew G. Haley had foreseen the definition of the upper limits of national sovereignty becoming a “first-class problem of international relations.”

Recent developments in private space travel have increased the need for a legal demarcation of the upper limit of sovereignty. Firstly, the number of artificial satellites orbiting the Earth has increased tremendously, and there has been a downward trend in the altitude of those satellites in recent years. This is mostly due to the increased proportion of satellites in Low Earth Orbit (LEO), which now account for around 84% of orbiting satellites,⁴ which, in turn, is mostly the result of satellite internet providers. Secondly, space is more important in general; there have now been numerous launches even outside of the Earth’s orbit with various countries possessing this ability as opposed to only the USSR and the US, militaries of the world have developed or are actively developing various capabilities to de-orbit objects, and there are now LEO-orbiting Satellites capable of detailed imagery of subjacent nations at a resolution of less than 1 meter.⁵ At that time of Haley’s writing, more than a hundred nations had asserted sovereignty over their superjacent airspace, but not a single one had established where “airspace” ends and “space” begins, treating terms such as “airspace” and “atmosphere” as synonymous. Haley noted that as of 1963, no nation had yet claimed sovereignty above the area of its sovereign “airspace” as set out in the *1927 Paris Convention*⁶ and the *1955 Convention on International Civil Aviation (Chicago Convention)*.⁷ Haley urged nations to eschew determination of this limit simply by *ex parte* statements and strive for a material definition of the border between sovereign airspace and “space.”

Haley focuses on what he terms the “von Karman jurisdictional line”, named after the famed aerodynamicist Dr. Theodore von Karman, who is ostensibly responsible for its calculation. In a paper delivered in the spring of 1957, Haley showed the below figure of the Karman line superimposed on a diagram made by Masson and Gazley of the Rand Corporation, illustrating the possible ranges for continuous flight in the velocity-altitude coordinate system.

Figure 1 - Diagram showing regimes of atmospheric and extra-atmospheric flight and depicting the jurisdictional boundary lines.

⁴ Jonathan C McDowell, ‘The Low Earth Orbit Satellite Population and Impacts of the SpaceX Starlink Constellation’ (2020) 892(2) *The Astrophysical Journal* L36, 2–3.

⁵ Alexandra Harris and Ray Harris, ‘The Need for Air Space and Outer Space Demarcation’ (2006) 22(1) *Space Policy* 3–4.

⁶ Convention for the Regulation of Aerial Navigation, opened for signature 13 October 1919, 7 LNTS 245 (entered into force 13 June 1922); Protocol of Amendment signed at Paris 17 February 1926, 26 LNTS 455 (entered into force 2 January 1927).

⁷ Convention on International Civil Aviation (Chicago Convention), opened for signature 7 December 1944, 15 UNTS 295 (entered into force 4 April 1947).

Haley claimed that “the scientific and jurisprudential considerations determining the line are entirely realistic, identifiable, and sufficient.” This line is intended to be a demarcation between the aeronautic and astronautic regions and is located at approximately 275,000 feet (83.82km) above sea level. Haley asserts that the exact distance is subject to change as it is to be defined as *the point at which an aeronautical vehicle may no longer perform*, and where “airspace” therefore no longer exists.

To support his view on the importance of a scientific basis for the line of demarcation, Haley quotes Dr. C. Wilfred Jenks: “no lawyer should indulge in abstract speculation on the subject without first familiarizing himself with the scientific background.” Haley then draws on a 1958 article by Jean Rivoire and extrapolates that the best solution would be one which meets these four requirements: 1) it does not present an obstacle to progress, 2) it is in accordance with the fundamental principles of law and the latest scientific data, 3) it is clear, simple and elastic and 4) it is harmonious with the international agreements, conventions, and treaties that are in force. Haley believed the von Karman line satisfies each of these points.

Haley then compares flights taken by the X-2 and the X-15 rocket-powered craft, explaining that the former flew at an altitude where 98% of its weight was carried by aerodynamic lift, and only 2% by centrifugal force, thereby making it an aeronautic flight. The latter, however, which flew 7,274 km/h at an altitude of 108,000 feet at with virtually no aerodynamic lift, passed the von Karman line and thus qualified as a spacecraft. The constraints within the Mason and Gazley diagram on an aeronautic flight are therefore defined by velocity and altitude. Velocity is limited at 5000 feet per second at sea level, as beyond this point the skin temperature of the aircraft reaches upwards of 2000 degrees Fahrenheit, which is outside of the capability of contemporary materials and cooling technology. This velocity constraint, in turn, limits the reachable altitude of a pilot-driven aircraft at 150,000 feet. Haley stated that:⁸

Between these two barriers there is a corridor of continuous flight which terminates when at an approximate speed of 25,000 feet per second (7.62km/s) and an altitude of about 275,000 feet, the Kepler force takes over and the aerodynamic lift is gone. This is a critical jurisdictional line, marking the theoretical limit of air flight, which is here termed the von Karman line.

Haley correctly predicted that with advances in technology, this line would change slightly, but that it would remain relatively consistent, despite advances in technology, and expressed hope that lawyers and engineers would inevitably agree on an altitude where an aerodynamic vehicle could no longer function by generating lift.

2. A SURVEY OF MAJOR WRITERS' VIEWS

Haley catalogues other notable authors' opinions on the upper limit of sovereignty. Firstly, he looks at Prof. John Cobb Cooper, who examines the suggestion of basing the territory of a state on that state's ability to exercise its authority over it. Establishing that this would mean the power of rich states would give them a higher upper limit to sovereignty vis-à-vis poorer states, and asking:

Can we be said to live in such a world where the physical power at any one time of any particular state determines its international right to consider the region above its surface territories as part of its national territory?⁹

Haley cites Cooper's belief that with the application of this rule, every state, regardless of power or size, should have territorial rights that extend “as high as the rights of every other State, no matter how powerful. Cooper also suggests a three-zone concept of sovereignty: First, a zone that extends from the

⁸ Andrew G Haley, *Space Law and Government* (Appleton-Century-Crofts 1963) 98.

⁹ *Ibid*, 83.

ground to a height where aircraft, as now defined, can operate, wherein a subjacent state has full sovereignty. Second, a zone that extends up to 300 miles above the Earth's surface, where a subjacent state exercises sovereignty in tandem with the right of transit for all non-military flights. And third, a zone that extends infinitely above the second zone, which would be "free for the passage of all instrumentalities." Cooper ultimately points to the necessity of an international agreement with which Dr. Alex Meyer agrees, arguing the necessity of treating outer space as a "free area like the open seas".

Haley then contrasts two other viewpoints, first made by G. P. Zadorozhnij, who argues for setting the limit below the zone in which satellites orbit, and that of Dr. Ming-Min Peng, who would extend sovereignty to the limits of all flights until interplanetary flight was possible. To this point, another author, Dr. C. Wilfred Jenks, argues that the realities of interstellar space make it "a meaningless and dangerous abstraction" due to the scale of the universe.¹⁰ Oscar Schachter poses questions as to how the term "air" should be defined and to which point it extends, concluding thus: "whatever may be the precise boundary of the airspace, it is clear that when we go beyond it, we are legally in a no man's world". Haley then points to John A. Johnson, who claims that the interests of subjacent states would not be served by the extension of their sovereignty to extremely high altitudes and that a form of international control over specific space activities is required instead, by using as an example the circulation of satellites over all nations without permission or protest, he reasons that nations have not regarded territorial sovereignty as extending to the point at which satellite orbit has occurred.

Haley also refers to Dr. Eugene Pepin, C. E. S. Horford, who contends that space should be considered similarly as the high seas and Bin Cheng who offers a similar view, Haley suggests that these three disagree with extending sovereignty into space and would "...allow its free use above a certain line—perhaps the von Karman line". Next to be mentioned are, firstly, Stephen Gorove, who agrees that expansion of sovereignty into space is untenable, stating, however, that the most pressing problem is the establishment of an international inspection system; and secondly, Captain George D. Schrader, who supports the von Karman line and argues for the need for it to be accepted by the United States and Russia. To be concurrently regulated with the help of the IAF and the IISL and then submitted to the United Nations. Haley also quotes the ruling of the Supreme Court in *United States v. Causby*:¹¹

It is an ancient doctrine that a common law ownership of the land extended to the periphery of the universe — *Cujus est solum ejus est usque ad coelum*. But that doctrine has no place in the modern world.

Lastly, Haley addresses the dissenting opinion of William Strauss, who argues that there is no agreement on the scientific facts, and that "...the top of the "atmosphere" has been estimated at anywhere from 10 to 650 miles (16 to 1050 km) above the earth's surface". To this, Haley stresses that the issue is not with the facts, which are widely accepted, but with deciding which facts are relevant and how their importance should be factored in creating the jurisdictional line.

Thus far, Haley stresses the necessity of a scientific solution to the limit of sovereignty versus an arbitrary political one. Haley explains the dangers of a political solution and alludes to the reluctance of states to give up power as the reason behind the lack of progress in the determination of the upper limit. To exemplify this, most states formally forbid the passage of military aircraft of any kind over their territory at any height, despite this being impossible to control or enforce due to the vastness of space. Haley mentions a June 1959 report by the United Nations *ad hoc* Committee on the Peaceful Uses of Outer Space (COPUOS), which deemed definitions of the upper limit to sovereignty to be premature,¹² and he quotes committee member George J. Feldman in the colloquium, stating that the

¹⁰ C Wilfred Jenks, 'International Law and Activities in Space' (1956) 5 *International and Comparative Law Quarterly* 103, 103–04.

¹¹ *United States v. Causby*, 328 U.S. 256 (1946).

¹² United Nations Ad Hoc Committee on the Peaceful Uses of Outer Space, 'Report of the Ad Hoc Committee on the Peaceful Uses of Outer Space' (June 1959) UN Doc A/4141E.

committee gave its approval to treating space as *res communis*.¹³ Haley's contemporary legal scholars, while torn on the exact point of termination of sovereignty, for the most were in agreement that "space", however that is to be defined, can either be *res communis* or *res nullius*, as those are the only practically possible solutions.

3. OTHER CRITIQUES TO THE VON KARMAN LINE

Haley points out that there are certain legal scholars who remained sceptical of the effectiveness of the Karman line since it does not create a definitive distinction between airspace and outer space. He responds to this claim by asserting that an approximate median may prove more beneficial than a rigid definition in many situations of ambiguity. Since there is an array of dynamic political, economic and military factors involved in the distinction between air law and space law, a purely spatial solution is purposeless.

3.1. *The Rocket Plane*

An objection that has been raised to the Von Karman line is that the delineation would be futile, given that there may be certain rocket-powered craft, such as the X-15, which will be able to travel to more than twice the altitude at which the aerodynamic lift subsides. Mr. Philip Quigg was the first to point out that such demarcation would not be practical if there were aircraft capable of coasting into the realm of satellites.¹⁴ He noted that the significance of such vehicles was that they obscured the distinction between air space and outer space. It is therefore clear that Mr. Quigg has adopted a more functional approach to the question of sovereignty, and his claims are rooted in the fact that there may be aircraft capable of travelling beyond the Karman line. Haley counters these propositions by stating that the X-15 is a rocket vehicle and not an aircraft; therefore, even if a functional definition is considered, the efficacy of the Karman line cannot be negated. He distinguishes between aircraft and spacecraft by outlining the technical, structural, and functional differences between the vehicles. An aircraft subsists on air and has not been designed to function in outer space, whereas a space vehicle does not subsist on air and merely uses air as a guidance aid on entry or departure. Although Mr. Quigg mentioned that the X-15 is a "winged craft and not a pure rocket", Haley counters this statement by asserting that the winged configuration does not determine whether it can be considered a rocket. Therefore, the existence of air guidance services does not necessarily mean that the vehicle is an aircraft. According to Haley, this would essentially imply that any object or vehicle which uses the Earth's air in any manner would not be a space vehicle. He argues as follows:

Under the assumptions of the Quigg approach, however, any vehicles – vehicles designed for earth orbiting or for voyages to the moon, the planets, and even the stars- would not be considered space vehicles if they used air guidance surfaces during the brief seconds of their departure from or return to the earth. Indeed, if they utilize the Earth's air in any fashion at all, it seems they would not be space vehicles.

3.2. *A Soviet Criticism*

The first full-scale treatise on space law, written by Feliks Nikolayevich Kovalev and Ivan Ivanovich Cheprov, dealt with certain aspects of the Karman Line.¹⁵ In Chapter 1 of the treatise, they criticize the Karman line as a means to determine the sphere of action of state sovereignty by means of coordinates of altitude and velocity. It is contended that the Karman line will be altered by alloys, and if a convertible airspace vehicle is created, the boundary would be "transformed into the most intricate and artful curve

¹³ Galloway, *The United Nations Ad Hoc Committee on the Peaceful Uses of Outer Space: Accomplishments and Implications for Legal Problems* (2d Colloq, Vienna, Springer-Verlag 1960) 30.

¹⁴ Philip W Quigg, 'Open Skies and Open Space' (October 1958) 37 *Foreign Affairs* 95–106.

¹⁵ FN Kovalev and II Cherpov, *Na puti k kosmicheskomu pravu* ['On the Path to Space Law'] (Izd-vo IMO, Moscow 1962).

with knots and loops”.¹⁶ The treatise notes that if there are foreign missiles and planes flying over a neutral state at the same altitude, the state could act against the former but not the latter. It is also argued that the Karman line does not consider actual flight possibilities. According to the authors, the Karman line also seems to ignore flight instrumentalities like ballistic missiles, which cannot be considered purely “transitional”.

Haley counters these claims by mentioning that the claims solely rely on the *1957 Masson-Gazley diagram*, which has been significantly altered and revised since then. He stated that the Karman line is a fixed horizontal line and is not represented by a curve as was claimed in the treatise. He also mentions that the boundary will change in due course of time with technological advancements and that it is impracticable that instrumentalities at the same altitude and geographical point can be considered to be in “airspace” and “cosmic space” simultaneously.

3.3. Alternative Approaches

Haley begins by noting that all satellites have at some point passed through the Karman line. Ballistic rockets and rocket-powered spacecraft are not constrained by aerodynamic lift support, which leads to an increased flight altitude. He concludes that only a very narrow corridor exists between air space and outer space. Essentially, there are three schemes of flight: the aviation regime, the corridor of atmospheric escape, and the astronautic regime. The aeronautical regime is regulated by the Chicago Convention, various other international laws, and domestic legislations, while the astronautic regime is ‘terra nullius’ or ‘no man’s land’. The primary question regards what regime can be made applicable to the escape corridor. Sanger was of the opinion that national jurisdiction should end at the beginning of the escape corridor. This can be compared with Dr. Cooper's idea of “contiguous zones”, in which there is a rite of passage to all non-military flights.¹⁷ However, a direct comparison cannot be drawn because Cooper’s upper limit was set at 300 miles, which would exclude a significant portion of the escape corridor.

Haley concedes that more research would be required before a conclusion can be reached with respect to whether direct control can be exercised for a limited stretch above the Karman line. Another approach to the problem was propounded by Eurico Fonseca, which is focused on the escape velocity of the vehicle as a determinant factor.¹⁸ Furthermore, G. Vernon Leopold and A.L. Scafuri have highlighted that the distinction is contingent on the demarcation between suborbital and orbital flight.¹⁹ Accordingly, it may be preferable to exempt vehicles from the territorial sovereignty of states, irrespective of the attained altitude, particularly when the eccentricity and angular momentum exceed the minimum threshold. However, if the momentum is reduced below the minimum threshold, they must be subject to national sovereignty of the underlying state.

4. CONTEMPORARY DEVELOPMENTS

4.1. Essential Features, Writers' Views, and Other Criticism

4.1.1. Technological development

From the perspective of technological development, many factors have increased the need for a legal demarcation of the upper limit to sovereignty. Firstly, the number of artificial satellites orbiting the Earth has increased tremendously, and there has been a downward trend in the altitude of those satellites in recent years. This is mostly due to the increased proportion of satellites in LEO, which now account

¹⁶ *Supra* note 8, 106.

¹⁷ See generally John Cobb Cooper and Ivan A Vlasic (eds), *Explorations in Aerospace Law: Selected Essays, 1946–1966* (McGill-Queen’s University Press, Montreal 1968).

¹⁸ See Eurico Sidónio Gouveia Xavier Lopes da Fonseca, *The Conquest of Space* (Lisbon: IMO, 1962).

¹⁹ G Vernon Leopold and AL Scafuri, ‘On the Boundary between Air Law and Space Law’ (abstract prepared for Andrew G Haley (ed), *Space Law and Government* (Appleton-Century-Crofts, New York 1963) 112).

for around 84% of orbiting satellites,²⁰ which, in turn, is mostly the result of satellite internet providers. Secondly, space is more important in general; there have now been numerous launches even outside of the Earth's orbit with various countries possessing this ability as opposed to only the USSR and the US, militaries of the world have developed or are actively developing various capabilities to de-orbit objects, and there are now LEO-orbiting Satellites capable of detailed imagery of subjacent nations at a resolution of less than 1 meter.²¹ Lastly, space travel has become accessible to the private sector, recently extending even to the tourist sector, which advertises travel to suborbital space using rocket-propelled aircraft.²²

However, the one factor that has still remained relatively constant is the capability of 'air breathing' aircraft. These have seemingly settled at a line that is significantly below the Haley suggested demarcation of 275,000 feet (~83km). The history of aircraft altitude progress can be seen in *Figure 1*, which should serve to ameliorate the concern of technological advance overcoming the von Karman line, at least with regards to "non-rocket" aircraft. That is because of the 3 evident facts: First, there is still a space of around 45 kilometers until we reach the originally defined von Karman line. Second, progress towards each subsequent kilometer proves more challenging, as can be observed by the flattening of the curve. Third, jet aircraft have not been able to progress a single kilometer higher in the last 45 years.²³

4.1.2. Jurisprudential development

While much progress has transpired in the 60 years following the publication of Andrew G. Haley's book, legal development has largely stagnated behind the technological. And this chapter, rather than representing a deviation, encapsulates the rule.

As for writing, a legal norm for the specific upper limit of sovereignty is yet to be established. That is despite the increasing importance of the issue during the progress of the space age, discussed below. Several nations have already used this lacuna to attempt to assert their sovereignty over outer space, such as the seven equatorial countries behind the *1976 Declaration of the First Meeting of Equatorial Countries on the Zone of the Geostationary Orbit* (Bogota Declaration),²⁴ mainly due to their strategic position below the geostationary orbit.²⁵ While the Bogota Declaration was of little consequence, perhaps a more important development is occurring in China and is best explained in the words of Mr. Phillip A. Meek in his address to the USCC:²⁶

From a legal perspective, the most troublesome indicators of China's apparent assertions of sovereignty in space are the increasing number of publications by influential Chinese authors advancing the principle that China's sovereign territory extends through outer space. As justification for the position, Chinese authors assert that their territorial claims to outer space are not inconsistent with international law because there is no internationally

²⁰ *Supra* note 4.

²¹ *Supra* note 5.

²² Debra Kamin, 'The Future of Space Tourism Is Now. Well, Not Quite' *The New York Times* (7 May 2022) <https://www.nytimes.com/2022/05/07/travel/space-travel-tourism.html>

²³ Rebecca Maksel, 'Who Holds the Altitude Record for an Airplane?' *Smithsonian Magazine* (2009) <https://www.smithsonianmag.com/air-space-magazine/who-holds-the-altitude-record-for-an-airplane-141522931/>

²⁴ Declaration of the First Meeting of Equatorial Countries on the Zone of the Geostationary Orbit ('Bogotá Declaration') (Bogotá, 8 November 1976) 15 ILM 493 (1976).

²⁵ Lawrence D Roberts, 'A Lost Connection: Geostationary Satellite Networks and the International Telecommunication Union' (2000) 15 Berk Tech LJ 1095.

²⁶ Phillip A Meek, 'Testimony Before the US-China Economic and Security Review Commission: China's Views of Sovereignty and Methods of Access Control' (Testimony, US-China Economic and Security Review Commission, 2018).

accepted definition of outer space that has a demarcation point at which national airspace ends, and outer space begins.

The year 1967 marked the ratification of the *Treaty on Principles Governing the Activities of States in the Exploration and Use of Outer Space, including the Moon and Other Celestial Bodies, opened for signature* (OST), which among other things, established space as *res communis*.²⁷ Thus, proving the majority of the authors discussed in Haley's book correct and casting away the more fringe theories of sovereignty '*ad coelum*'. However, the OST fell short of defining the point at which this demarcation between airspace and space happens. The U.S. FAA and NASA use a 50-mile limit,²⁸ whereas international regulatory agencies such as the FAI,²⁹ the U.S. Air Force and Space Force, as well as the governments of Denmark, Australia, and Kazakhstan, through their respective space legislations, have established the limit at 100km.³⁰ In some of these cases, this 100km limit is termed the von Karman line.

The author Thomas Gangale, in his article 'The Non-Karman Line: An Urban Legend of the Space Age', doubts the validity of the origin of this jurisdictional line, as well as its calculation. According to Gangale, Haley himself frequently and substantially changed not only the distance to the line itself, but also the methodology describing the line, basing it on various unrelated physical phenomena. Gangale suggests that since von Karman had numerous contemporaries whose own interpretations of a boundary were more closely matched with the now accepted 100km, it is not merely unreasonable to attribute it to von Karman, but in doing so, perhaps unintentionally it uses the famous aerodynamicist to attribute a "scientific basis" to a political concept.³¹ Gangale also discusses a lack of any proof that Theodore von Karman ever worked on such a calculation.³²

The aerospace engineer Nicolas Bérend focused in his work on finding the 'missing calculation' behind the von Karman line and suggested that Haley may have merely received the diagram from von Karman, without any explanation. Bérend also calls attention to numerous apparent points of confusion of the underlying physics.³³ The astrophysicist Jonathan McDowell further investigates the basis of the 100km "von Karman line" and referring to the FAI document '*100 km Altitude Boundary for Astronautics*' he states: "it is unfortunate that discussion in this official document in the section 'demonstration of usefulness of Karman line' appears to be poorly researched".³⁴ McDowell thereafter establishes that the induction by which the FAI came to the 100km's, if applied correctly, would lead to an 80km Karman Line instead. Following the publication of this article by McDowell, the FAI released a statement on its von Karman page, acknowledging the research (though not explicitly), and proposing an international workshop in 2019.³⁵ However, no further updates have been given on the page since.

²⁷ Treaty on Principles Governing the Activities of States in the Exploration and Use of Outer Space, including the Moon and Other Celestial Bodies, opened for signature 27 January 1967, 610 UNTS 205 (entered into force 10 October 1967).

²⁸ Thomas Gangale, 'The Non Karman Line: An Urban Legend of the Space Age' (2017) 41 Journal of Space Law 151, 152-155.

²⁹ S Sanz Fernández de Córdoba, '100 km Altitude Boundary for Astronautics' (Fédération Aéronautique Internationale, 2004) <https://www.fai.org/page/icare-boundary>

³⁰ Anon, 'Near Space: The Quest for a New Legal Frontier' (2021) 13 International Association for the Advancement of Space Safety, 2.

³¹ *Supra* note 21, 159-62, 177.

³² *Supra* note 21, 167.

³³ Nicolas Bérend, 'The Missing Calculation behind the Original Kármán Line Definition – A Credible Hypothesis' in Proceedings of the *International Astronautical Congress 2021* (Dubai, United Arab Emirates, 2021) 2-4.

³⁴ Jonathan C McDowell, 'The Edge of Space: Revisiting the Kármán Line' (2018) 151 Acta Astronautica 668, 3.

³⁵ Anon, 'Statement about the Kármán Line' (Fédération Aéronautique Internationale, 2018) <https://www.fai.org/news/statement-about-karman-line> accessed 10 May 2022.

4.2. Alternative Approaches

Haley suggests numerous alternative approaches to the issue of jurisdiction. Some of these approaches will be analyzed in line with the various technological and scientific developments that have taken place since his book was written.

To some extent, Professor Gangale countered the approach taken by Haley in his book “*How High the Sky? The Definition and Delimitation of Outer Space and Territorial Airspace in International Law*”.³⁶ Gangale acknowledges two main approaches to the question of limiting sovereignty. Firstly, a spatial approach which sets a specific altitude, delineating where sovereign airspace ends and where outer space begins. Secondly, a functional approach by which space law is deemed to be applicable based on the activities that are conducted, regardless of where these activities occur. Haley and Gangale do not diverge on this point. Gangale does, however, highlight the immediacy of the need to answer the question of delimitation, especially given that private space flight and suborbital transportation are on the rise. He holds that the *ad coelum* doctrine is untenable because space vehicles may travel from one superjacent area to another, and the rotation of the Earth makes it difficult to create a vertical upper limit. Later, the *ad coelum* doctrine was overruled, and space was considered to be the common heritage of mankind.

Apart from the Karman line, there have been other approaches to determine a vertical limit to national sovereignty.

4.2.1. The political approach

Gangale notes that sovereignty is distinguishable from independence and control,³⁷ with the latter being essentially a subset of sovereignty. Every state has the right to exercise exclusive control over activities that take place in its airspace.³⁸ The effective control theory is a political theory; however, it is pertinent to note that it is purely conceptual because no altitude of control has ever been proposed.

According to the state interest theory, the limits of sovereignty extend until the point at which state interest exists. Therefore, state interests would logically end at the uppermost limits of the atmosphere.³⁹ The interest theory is closely related to the test of effective control since states normally exercise control over territory that they have an interest in.

4.2.2. The spatial approach

As the name suggests, the spatial approach proposes a delineation on the basis of a specified boundary at a defined altitude. This approach does not take into consideration the types of activities that are carried out in air space or outer space. There are three different arguments within this approach: the technical argument, the arbitrary argument, and the combined approach. An arbitrary single boundary is a 12 nautical mile limit of vertical sovereignty, similar to the territorial sea model. The problem with this approach is that certain states may have the technical capabilities to operate beyond the arbitrary single boundary. Additionally, the role of physical phenomena such as gravitational pull, escape velocity and atmospheric physics on the spatial approach cannot be ignored. Bin Cheng has noted as follows:⁴⁰

³⁶ Thomas Gangale, *How High the Sky?: The Definition and Delimitation of Outer Space and Territorial Airspace in International Law* (Leiden: Brill Nijhoff 2018).

³⁷ *Ibid*, 32.

³⁸ Hans Kelsen, *General Theory of Law and State* (Routledge, London 1945).

³⁹ JFL Nijeholt, *Air Sovereignty* (1st edn, Springer Science Dordrecht 1910) 46.

⁴⁰ Bin Cheng, *Recent Developments in Air Law* (Vol 12, 1956) 208.

Airspace is the entire space where air is to be found under any form. This is identical with the atmosphere in its broadest meaning, including all of its layers, irrespective of whether it is sufficiently dense to carry aircraft.

Beyond these conventional approaches, certain scholars have even suggested a variable 30-statute mile limit during times of peace and a 4030-statute mile limit during times of war.⁴¹

There has also been an attempt to define the region above and adjacent to national airspace as “near space” extending 18 km above sea level to 160 km above sea level (International Association for the Advancement of Space Safety 2020:10).⁴² This approach takes inspiration from the demarcation provided under UNCLOS by which the continental shelf, contiguous zone and exclusive economic zone were created to protect the safety and security of the coastal state and also to prevent exploitation of economic resources in the adjacent areas to the territorial waters. Near space is not considered to be a part of the national territory of the state, however, there are certain restrictions that are placed on other states operating in this area. While there is a right to innocent passage for civil and commercial activities, there is a right of the underlying state to utilize and administer the near space to the exclusion of other states.⁴³

4.2.3. Functional approach

The functional approach focuses on the activities that are conducted in outer space to better understand the jurisdictional scope of space law. It must be noted that the security interests of states and the right to self-defense are inextricably intertwined with the functional approach. Lipson and Katzenbach have asserted that all states must have the unfettered right to exercise jurisdiction over military satellites and space vehicles in their superjacent airspace, while also ensuring that the right to free passage of other non-military satellites and vehicles is protected.⁴⁴ Thus, proponents of the functional approach do not advocate in favor of demarcation but argue that jurisdictional concerns are correlated to the purposes for which the vehicle or object is used. There is a general consensus that certain activities (testing nuclear weapons, changing the composition of outer space, establishing military bases, etc.) must not be permitted. However, the primary issue with this approach is the failure to establish a reasonable standard of what constitutes a “space activity”. The only definition that can be reached is that all launches into outer space, as well as any other ancillary activities conducted while the vehicle is in outer space, may be considered space activities.

4.2.4. Gangale’s approach

Gangale’s approach appears to be a coalescence of various other approaches. He alludes to a “conventional solution” by which states must engage in negotiations to draft an international legal instrument that delineates between air law and space law rather than giving effect to any conceptual principle. Owing to the complexity of technological and scientific criteria, a practical solution to resolve the persisting issue is for states to arrive at a mutual agreement. Without a clear definition, there may be conflict regarding the allocation of positions in geostationary orbits and other associated issues like the uniform aerospace regime.

Another solution that he refers to is what he calls a “hybrid solution”. There are two primary questions which must be answered then: where does outer space begin, and where does spatial sovereignty end? Both questions must be determined separately. A consensus seems to have been reached in terms of determining the lower limit of space law. It is clear that international space law applies to any satellite that orbits around the Earth; hence, logically, space law must begin at the lowest possible altitude at

⁴¹ Lipson L and Katzenbach N, *Außen Politik. Zeitschrift für Internationale Fragen* vol 8 (1961) 43.

⁴² International Association for the Advancement of Space Safety, ‘Near Space: The Quest for a New Legal Frontier’ (2020) 13, 10.

⁴³ *Ibid*, 11.

⁴⁴ See *supra* note 34.

which a satellite can stay in orbit. Thus, airspace sovereignty cannot extend beyond this lower limit, i.e. beyond the lowest point at which a satellite is capable of remaining in orbit. Earlier, one of the criticisms of this theory was that it would be difficult to monitor the altitude of satellites at a given point of time, however, this has been resolved with the advent of global navigation satellite system technology.

The lower limit or “lowest perigee theory” has a direct impact on the right to free access to outer space and will therefore affect the upper limit of state sovereignty. Security threats and increased military activities in outer space are also determinant criteria in settling the upper limit. It remains to be seen whether a feasible solution can be reached that resolves the trade-off between security concerns and the right to free passage. However, since all space objects travel through the atmosphere upon their return, there is a need to differentiate between air law and space law on the basis of the intended function of the vehicle.

5. CONCLUSION

The subject matter of a vertical limit to sovereignty has been extensively studied and analyzed by legal scholars and scientists, who have created an impressive array of approaches. Unfortunately, despite the ever-increasing need for the upper limit of sovereignty to be formally defined, it currently still remains undefined in international law. There are, however, two points of consolation. Firstly, the OST, which is now widely considered customary international law, at least establishes that wherever space begins, state sovereignty ends. Concurrently, the most widely used point to refer to where space begins seems to be at 100km. Secondly, the lack of state disputes over satellite orbits superjacent to their territory may suggest yet another custom in formation. For these reasons, it seems superfluous to these authors to give any further recommendations at this time.

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